

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND PRODUCTIVITY OF LIBRARIANS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN NIGERIA: A CORRELATIONAL APPROACH

Japheth Abdulazeez Yaya¹ⁱ,

Oluseyi A. Akintayo², Chioma Euriel Uzohue³

¹Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, P.M.B. 4008, Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria

²Senior Assistant Registrar, Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria

³Chief Librarian, Nigerian Institute of Medical Research, Yaba, Lagos State, Nigeria

Abstract:

This study investigated emotional intelligence as correlates of productivity of librarians in Nigerian public universities. A correlational survey research design was adopted. The study population consisted of 1,254 librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria, from which 923 were selected using simple random sampling. The research instrument used was a self-developed questionnaire. The questionnaire validation was subjected to the scrutiny of the experts in the areas of the variables studied; it gave a reliability coefficient of 0.91 for Emotional Intelligence and 0.94 for Productivity. A response rate of 67.2% was achieved. Data were analysed using descriptive (percentage, mean, average mean and standard deviation) and inferential (Pearson Product Moment Correlation) statistics. The study revealed a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity ($r = 0.032$, $P < 0.05$) of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria. The study concluded that contrary to general belief, emotional intelligence and productivity levels of librarians in university libraries were high. It is recommended that university library management should continue to promote values that would improve emotional intelligence and productivity of its workforce.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, librarians' productivity, productivity in public university libraries, emotional intelligence competencies

ⁱ Corresponding author: Japheth Abdulazeez Yaya, PhD e-mail yjapheth@yahoo.com

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Emotional intelligence of employees plays a crucial role in enhancing the general productivity of workers in any organization especially in the university libraries where librarians on daily basis meet with diverse information seekers for their various information needs. Productivity according to Parham (2014) can be defined as a measure of the rate at which outputs of goods and services are produced per unit of input (labour, capital, raw materials, etc). It is calculated as the ratio of the amount of outputs produced to some measure of the amount of inputs used. In the same vein, Ogunsanwo (2012) defined productivity as the rate at which a worker, an organization, or a country produces goods and services. Employee productivity is generally acknowledged as a necessary factor that enhances the growth and development of every organization in the human society.

However, some employees may not be productive as expected of them by their employers due to the negative attitude displayed by them towards their employers. There is a general belief that man has the natural tendency to be lazy with regard to work and he is being forced by circumstances to work. This idea about man still continues to create problems for the development process of society in the face of abundant human and material resources resulting to low productivity.

Low productivity is generally observed as a major problem that presently thrives in many organizations particularly in the developing countries. Some scholars (Ajala, 2012; Dost, Rehman & Tariq, 2012; Suleiman, 2013; Yamoah, 2013; Ali et al, 2013, among others) investigated what constitutes low productivity among workers in different organizations; the results of their findings showed that majority of the employees had issues with their organizations ranging from perceived problem of inadequate attention to their basic needs by the organization to feelings of being marginalized, unfair treatment by their employers; some employees' productivity problems are within the work environment such as irregular and non-payment of salaries and wages, lack of working tools, uncomfortable office design and preferential treatment of some set of employees at the expense of other members of staff in the organization while some had attitudinal and emotionally related issues which greatly affected their productivity. It can be deduced from their studies that conducive work environment stimulates employees' creativity and increases their performance substantially while bad working conditions contribute to low productivity of employees in many organizations. The public university libraries in Nigeria cannot be isolated from these ugly phenomena as it is generally observed that the level of productivity in

most public university libraries today is low due to job dissatisfaction of its personnel especially the librarians (Babalola & Nwalo, 2013).

Thus, in this study, productivity is conceptualized to mean the ability to produce an item or service in the organization. Also, it refers to all efforts that an individual employee exerts towards the general production of goods and services of the organization with the least input of skills, labour, material, and machines. In Nigerian public university libraries, librarians' productivity entails providing current and relevant educational resources in the library that would encourage increase in paper publications among faculty members and librarians themselves, innovative research works in the university that would attract grants from both local and international organizations, among other accrued benefits. This helps in promoting the image and status of the university among her peers. Hence, it becomes logical that librarians should be adequately and motivated by their employers they are to be emotionally stabled if they are to increase the rate of their productivity in the university system.

Emotional intelligence is a psychological term that enables an individual to know and manage his or her feelings and emotions and use this information to guide his/her thinking and action while relating with other people in the organization and in the larger society. EI skills are essential in determining not only employee job commitment and job satisfaction, but also the level of employee productivity in the organization (Masrek et al, 2012). EI enhances higher level of inter-relationships, mutual understanding and greater productivity at the work place. EI is broadly classified into four components: self-awareness, self-management, social-awareness and relationship management. Each of these has some number of indicators that enhance the productivity of workers in the organization. Twenty six of these emotional intelligence competencies are highlighted and discussed in this study in relation to productivity of librarians in the university library. It is a known fact that librarians on daily basis relate with different categories of library users that have diverse feelings and emotions. Thus, it is expected of every librarian to possess some measurements of emotional intelligence competencies (EICs) that would enable him or her to adequately meet the information needs of library users.

In Nigeria, there are eighty one (81) public universities (National University Commission, 2015). The list comprises of forty one (41) Federal universities and forty (40) State owned universities. Moreover, these universities are spread amongst the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria. In the South-West zone there are eight (8) Federal universities and 10 State universities; in the South-South zone there are seven (7) Federal universities and 7 State universities; in the South-East zone there are 6 Federal universities and five (5) State universities; in the North-Central zone there are 8 Federal

universities and 6 State universities; North-East zone has 6 Federal universities and 5 State universities; while North-West zone has eleven (11) Federal universities and 7 State universities respectively. Each of these public universities have a library manned by a University Librarian working together with other professional librarians to provide relevant educational resources to support the curricula of the university programmes.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Research has shown that the level of job satisfaction and productivity of library personnel is low (Babalola & Nwalo, 2013) although their research productivity is relatively high (Okonedo, Popoola, Emmanuel & Bamigboye, 2015). While many of these studies have been directed towards library use, library collections and library services, few if any have been carried out from the perspective of personal welfare of employees. In other words, studies have not been directed at investigating the relationships between welfare and personal issues such as emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in public universities. The aim of this research is to find out the relationships among these variables; specifically, the extent to which emotional intelligence correlates with the productivity of librarians in university libraries in Nigeria.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The general objective of this research work is to investigate how emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in Nigerian public university libraries are correlated. The specific objectives are to:

1. Find out the level of productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria;
2. Assess the level of emotional intelligence of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria;
3. Evaluate the relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria;
4. Find out the challenging issues in job satisfaction and productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

The following are the list of research questions slated for this research work:

1. What is the level of productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria?

2. What is the level of emotional intelligence of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria?
3. What challenges face librarians' job satisfaction and productivity in public university libraries in Nigeria?

1.5 Hypothesis

The null hypothesis for this study was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study is limited to librarians in the public (that is, federal and state) universities in Nigeria. This means that private universities and other third level institutions were excluded. Respondents were librarians in the federal and state universities that are spread across the six geopolitical regions in Nigeria. Para-professional staffers as well as other personnel of the libraries were thus excluded because the researcher believed that librarians are the custodians of information resources that are kept in the university library; they are the policy makers as well as managers of other library personnel. The study examined all the four emotional intelligence (EI) components as well as twenty six (26) EI competencies that relate to job satisfaction and productivity of librarians while those EI competencies of other library personnel were excluded.

2. Review of Literature

This portion is devoted to the review of literatures related to this study. The review is done under the following sub-headings:

2.1 Conceptual Discourse

The conceptual discourse for the study deals with all variables that constitute the study. In this study, dependent variable includes productivity; this forms the crux of the study, while the independent variable consists of emotional intelligence. These were discussed in the systematic order so as to give conceptual understanding of the study.

2.2 Productivity

Generally, "productivity is a concept that depends on the context in which it employed. It is a ratio to measure how well an organization (or individual, industry, country) converts input resources (labour, materials & machines) into goods and services" (Ali et al, 2013, p. 68. Productivity is a ratio to measure how well an organization (or

individual, industry) converts input resources (labour, materials & machines) into goods and services. This is usually expressed in ratios of inputs to outputs. Similarly, Chaudhary and Sharma (2012) as well as Rolloos (1997) cited in Ali et al (2013) posited productivity as that which people can produce with the least (smallest) amount of effort. It is the rate of power to produce, but productivity from the management or economic point of view is the ratio of what is produced to what is required to produce it. While in the librarianship point of view, they are tangible services which every librarian is expected to perform in order to satisfy the information needs of his/her clientele.

In this study, the researcher conceptualized productivity as the ability to produce an item or service in the organization. Also, he sees it as efforts that an individual employee exerts towards the general production of goods and services of the organization with the least input of labour, material, and machines. In any organization, productivity is important because it allows the business to be more cost effective. The more output a business has for a specific cause, the cheaper it is to produce the product. This in turn allows the business to have a higher profit. Productivity on the part of employees is important because getting your job done will help the company's growth. If the company grows and progresses, profits will increase. If profits in the company increase, not only will the bosses be happier but they will hire more people and give increase benefits to the employees. Thus, productivity is good to everyone and serves as an important ingredient for the survival and sustainable growth of every organization.

However, Olomolaiye, Wahaband Price (1998) and Gundecha (2012) classified the productivity factors into two categories: external factors the ones outside the control of the organization management and internal factors related to the productivity factors originating within the organization. From their viewpoint, the nature and composition of the organization are the internal factors that can enhance the productivity of workers in such organization. In the university system, there are three categories of workers: academic staff, senior staff and junior staff. Librarians are classified as part of the academic staff of the university system. Every professional librarian is expected to be productive. In the university libraries, librarians are saddled with the responsibility of selecting, acquiring and organizing library educational materials for easy accessibility and retrieval by the library users as well as rendering reference and selective dissemination of information (SDI) services to meet the information needs of library users. Unfortunately, some public university authorities are not treating her faculty members equally; there are some allowances that are paid to lecturers which are regarded by the university management as “*core academic staff*” in the university but which are not extended to librarians. It could be noted that with such composition, the

morale of librarians in such university will be low and this will invariably affect their productivity.

2.3 Emotional Intelligence

Mayer and Salovey (1990) defined emotional intelligence as the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate amongst them and to use the information to guide one's thinking and action. While Bar-On (2000) posited emotional intelligence as "an array of non-cognitive capabilities, competencies and skills that influences one's ability to succeed in coping with environmental demands and pressures" (p. 2). Also, Goleman (1998, n.p) asserted that emotional intelligence is a "learned capability based on competencies that results in outstanding performance at work". In fact, emotional intelligence implies the recognition of one's own feelings and that of other's as well as using it to make the best possible decisions in one's life (Hoseyni, 2005 cited in Rahgozar et al, 2012). In the university library, librarians make several decisions on the collections to be acquired into the library, accurate classification schemes to be used in organizing the library resources for easy accessibility and retrieval, library budgets and other decisions that enhance smooth running of the university library system. Ogungbeni, Ogungbo and Yaya (2013) affirmed that the work of the librarian is a service delivery one, on daily basis; rendering services to people from different backgrounds, cultures, feelings/emotions, skills and characters. As a result of this librarians must have knowledge on how to manage their emotions and render effective services to these "wonderful" library users that consult their collections for an information need or the other.

However, before continuing in the overview of emotional intelligence, it may be useful to take a slight detour and look at the word emotion. While the precise definition of emotion may be debated by psychologists, Goleman (1995b) used the term to refer to a human feeling and its distinctive thoughts, psychological and biological states, and range of propensities to act. He notes that the main categories or families of emotions are: anger, sadness, fear, enjoyments, love, surprise, disgust, and shame. These core families are the key components to consider when examining emotional intelligence and form the frame for further analysis. Therefore, emotional intelligence (EI) refers to the ability to perceive, control and evaluate emotions. Some researchers suggest that emotional intelligence can be learned and strengthened, while others claim it is an innate characteristic (Ogungbeni et al, 2013).

The importance of emotional intelligence (EI) has been well-documented in many literatures. The Emotional Intelligence skills can be defined as the competency in recognizing and managing our feelings and that of other people. Hence, EI skills have

gradually become more relevant to both workplace growth and people improvement (Khokhar & Kush, 2009). Singh (2005) listed 25 different competencies to be required in different professions, which included librarians. Despite extensive studies that have been carried out by many scholars on EI in several settings, e.g. banking sector (Wae, 2010); mental health institutions (Nikolaou & Tsaousis, 2002); public accounting firms (Chia, 2005); governmental organizations (Ghoniem et al., 2011); as well as professionals like policemen (Afolabi & Omole, 2010); teachers (Craig, 2008; Yahyazadeh-Jeloudar & Lotfi-Goodarzi, 2012; Orluwene & Wachikwu, 2014); ballet dancers (Petrides, Niven & Mouskounti, 2006); salespeople (Rozell, Pettijohn & Parker, 2004), debt collectors (Bachman et al, 2000), medical professionals (Affandi & Raza, 2013), real estate professionals (Swanson & Zobisch, 2014), final year undergraduate students (Maraichelvi & Rajan, 2013) and managers (Avci, Altindag & Yarbag, 2014), unfortunately, it is very rare to find study on EI in the context of library services. No doubt, several past studies that attempted to study the EI among librarians e.g. Budd (2007), Mill and Lodge (2006) and Yaya (2007) had explored the EI among academic librarians; Browne, George-Curran and Smith (2005) studied the EI among law librarians while Hernon, Giesecke and Alire (2007) studied emotional intelligence and its components in academic libraries. Recently, Abdullah-Sani et al (2013) studied emotional intelligence profile of public librarians in Malaysia where in their findings; they suggested appropriate training that would increase EI level among librarians. However, they were not as comprehensive as studies that were carried out in other professions such as bankers (Wae, 2010); government servants (Ghoniem, 2011); policemen (Afolabi & Omole, 2010), teachers (Craig, 2008; Yahyazadeh-Jeloudar & Lotfi-Goodarzi, 2012) and undergraduate final year students (Maraichelvi & Rajan, 2013).

Furthermore, Mayer and Salovey (1990) proposed a model that identified four different factors of emotional intelligence: the perception of emotion, reasoning with emotions, the ability to understand emotion and the ability to manage emotions:

Perceiving Emotions: The first step in understanding emotions is to accurately perceive them. In many cases, this might involve understanding nonverbal signals such as body language and facial expressions.

Reason for using Emotions: The next step involves using emotions to promote thinking and cognitive activity. Emotions help prioritize what we pay attention and react to; we respond emotionally to things that garner our attention.

Understanding Emotions: The emotions that we perceive can carry a wide variety of meanings. If someone is expressing angry emotions, the observer must interpret the cause of their anger and what it might mean. For example, if your boss is

acting angrily it might mean that he is dissatisfied with your work, or it could be because he got a speeding ticket on his way to work that morning or that he's been fighting with his wife.

Managing Emotions: The ability to manage emotions effectively is a key part of emotional intelligence. Regulating emotions, responding appropriately and responding to the emotions of others are all important aspects of emotional management.

However, the major impact that this model has on this study is that it helps librarians to know, monitor and control their feelings and emotions, discriminate among them and use the information to guide their thinking and actions in dealing with various people that visit the library for their educational needs. These people are of different character, some are highly temperamental and lousy; while some are quiet and easy going. Hence, with the knowledge of emotional intelligence, librarian must be able to manage these people's behaviour and render efficient services to them.

So what exactly did Goleman (1995a) meant by “emotional intelligence”? His first book set out a laundry list of desirable qualities, including self-confidence, sensitivity, self-awareness, self-control, empathy, optimism, and social skills. Indeed Zeidner, Mathews & Roberts (2009) criticized Goleman for listing almost every positive quality that was not actually cognitive intelligence. Subsequently Goleman (2002) sought to put the traits that focally define EI on a more systematic basis. This basic scheme is reproduced in Goleman’s model that suggests two key divisions separating deferent aspects of EI. First, are those elements of EI that refer to personal competencies (e.g. self-awareness) from those that related to social competencies (e.g. empathy). This distinction corresponds to Zeidner et al (2009) intrapersonal and interpersonal competencies. Second, are distinguished facets of EI that relate to awareness from those that concern the management and regulation of emotion.

In contrast, Goleman (1998) defined emotional intelligence as a set of learned skills that may translate directly into success in various social domains, such as the workplace. For example, the empathy competence helps team leaders to understand the feelings of team members, leading to greater team effectiveness. This same competence helps the librarian to be able to “read” the library user’s emotional reactions to a given information product and services. Besides, it would enable librarians to select and process a more relevant educational resource that would meet the information needs of users. Conversely, emotionally unintelligent behaviours may be highly damaging to organizations. Dubre (2013) noted, “the primary reason employees leave a company is poor management-people don’t quit organizations, they quit managers” (p. 58); so, if the emotion of library users are poorly managed by the librarians, they will stop patronizing the library and its collections. Thus, librarians should have detailed

knowledge of his/her emotions and manage it properly so that he/she can render effective services to the library clientele.

3. Employee Productivity and Effects of Emotional Intelligence Competencies on Librarians

Many studies had been conducted by some scholars to establish the relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of employees in the organization; few of these studies are here presented in this study. Sahdat, Saijad, Farooq and Rehman (2011); in their study concluded that high emotional intelligence employees between managers can manage the levels of work life; and that there is a need to develop emotional Intelligence competencies in persons to improve administrative performance and practices. Kahtani (2013) in his study affirmed that Employee Emotional Intelligence enhances Employee Performance in the Higher Education Institutions in Saudi Arabia; he concluded the study by proposing a theoretical framework highlighting the link between emotional intelligence (EI) and performance.

Orluwene and Wachikwu (2014) revealed in the findings of their study that emotional intelligence had a significant prediction for teachers job involvement implies that emotional intelligence is a key factor to development of positive interpersonal and interpersonal relationship and that it is a good component of motivators. It also helps to trigger empathetic feeling and social relations. The finding also revealed significant value for all the four dimensions of emotional intelligence, self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relationship management implies that both interpersonal and intrapersonal competence of emotional intelligence are key factors to being resilient in the face of some stressful work like that of the teachers. And that emotion is contagious.

In a related development, from the study conducted by Zaki, Hasan and Manzoor (2012) on the influence of emotional intelligence on employees' leadership skills – strategic approach towards organizational stability; it was concluded that the positive involvement of leadership effectiveness with properly utilized components of emotional intelligence (self-regulation, empathy, recognition, motivation and communal skills) will enhance the organizational productivity and performance. Still on emotional intelligence components, EBSCO Competency Center (2013) further explained EI competencies like Self-regulation: When faced with problems and crises, managers and executives who self-regulate react thoughtfully and focus on causes and possible solutions. Motivation: Managers (librarians) with motivation excel, and they inspire their subordinates to also excel. Empathy: Empathy enables team leaders

(librarians) to assess team members' (subordinates') agendas and feelings, accommodate cultural differences when working with clients and colleagues, and more effectively motivate them. Social skill: Socially skilled managers and executives can rally employees to achieve business goals and transform vision into reality.

In the same vein, Goleman (2005) asserted in his book that mixed model of Emotional Intelligence operates under the assumption that it can be used to enhance the performance and effectiveness of individuals. He posited that emotional competencies are learned capabilities that must be worked on and developed to achieve outstanding performance. Again, that, individuals are born with a general Emotional Intelligence that determines their potentials for learning, achieving and performing (Goleman, 1998). Hence, this researcher concurs with these authors' submissions; as a librarian who possesses the emotional skills like empathy, recognition of other employees feelings and develop strategies in motivating workforce that are under his leadership will achieve higher level of productivity than his counterparts that possess less degree of emotional intelligence leadership skills. Swanson and Zobisch (2014) posited that EI has proven to be an effective skill leading to an individual's overall success in the workplace.

Besides, Salovey and Mayer (1990) primarily characterized most popular ability models of emotional intelligence in relationship to the manager's performance in the organization as a set of four exact cognitive natural forces that enhance his capability to recognize, cause with and utilize strong sentiments effectively. Specifically, he must possess the proficiencies to: perceive emotion; integrate emotion to facilitate thought; understand emotions; and manage emotions of his subordinates and clients so as to enhance his productivity in the organization. In support of Salovey's submission, it can be noted that emotional intelligence is a basic ability for learning and a key feature for efficient leadership (Yong, 2013; Javidparvar, Hosseini & Berjisian, 2013). Managing emotions by skills of controlling motions has relationship with managing through emotions. Managing emotions practically is related to how individuals behave with each other especially in the workplace or in the entire human society; therefore, in educational organizations such as the university library, librarian's roles in processing and disseminating relevant information to the information seekers are considered important. This skill helps individuals in self-regulation, being responsible to others, respecting others' views and articulating feelings. Managing emotions is a skill which approves the importance of leadership status in determining educational tasks, performing educational process sufficiently and self-esteem (Javidparvar et al, 2013).

However, from the findings of a study carried out by an unknown author it was discovered that emotional intelligence of employees had an impact on their level of job

performance. This has implications for management, suggesting that organizations could be profitable by identifying the level of emotional intelligence of employees and apply interventions that are focused on the developing emotional intelligence among the employees in the organization (Anonymous author, n.d). The author further stressed that EI is associated with better performance in the following areas: participative management; pulling people at ease; balance between personal life and work; straight forwardness and composure; decisiveness; doing whatever it takes to succeed; adaptability and confronting problem of the employees in the organization. He noted that most of the organizations employ employees that are emotionally intelligent, so that they can face the workplace problems easily and can be more productive for the organization.

Similarly, Javidparvar et al (2013) noted that EI influences organizational effectiveness in a number of areas such as: employee recruitment and retention; development of talent; teamwork; employee commitment; morale and health; innovation; productivity; efficiency; sales; revenues generations; quality of service; customer loyalty and client or student outcomes. He argued that the influence of EI begins with the retention and recruitment of talented workforce in the organization. Also, from the study of Krishnakumar and Lalitha (2014) on Emotional Intelligence and occupational stress; it was discovered that emotional intelligent people do extremely well at the work place; EI provides better understanding of work environment that reduce occupational stress. The authors further opined that occupational stress exist everywhere in an organization and in all the level of its workers. It can be observed that if the occupational stress is not properly managed by the manager in any organization, it can lead to a serious health condition and it can eventually lead to untimely demise of an experience employee in the organization. The management should be reminded that 'health is wealth'. Without it, nothing (including achieving the organizational stated goals) can be done. Therefore, the management crew should be emotionally intelligent.

The researcher concurs with these authors' submissions as they further reinforced his earlier position that there is strong link between EI and productivity of workers in any organization especially in the university library; librarians should be emotionally intelligent due to the nature of their duties as managers of human (users & library staff) and custodians of educational resources stocked in the university library. Therefore, they should be in total control of their moods and feelings so that they can manage the emotions of other people under their leadership in the university library. Also, every librarian should be emotionally intelligent so that they can be skilful in managing the occupational stress that abounds in the university library due to the nature of his work. This helps in improving the general health condition of the library

staff and eventually enhances their overall productivity in the entire university community which the university library intends to serve.

Generally, the Emotional Intelligence (EI) is made up of the following five main components: Self-Awareness, Social Awareness, Self-Management and Relationship Management. Interestingly, these EI components are inter-connected and they are further divided into some minor sets known as emotional intelligence competencies (EICs). Emotional intelligence competences (EICs) are what result and enhance our personal, relational and professional performance, and what ultimately help us attain an overall increase in our quality of life (Ziv, 2014). In a related development, Goleman (2002) defined Emotional Competence as a learned ability grounded in Emotional Intelligence. Goleman (2002) reviewed his earlier work of 1998 and later collapsed most of the EICs; nonetheless this study adapts Goleman (1998) framework as well as that of Ziv (2014) model; thus, the researcher shall discuss twenty six EICs in relationship to job satisfaction and productivity of librarians in the university library. The five main EI components with the twenty six EICs used for this study are succinctly presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1: A Framework of Emotional Intelligence Components showing Twenty Six Competencies used for this study

	Self-personal competence	Other social competence
Recognition	<p>Self-Awareness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emotional self-awareness - Accurate self-assessment/evaluation - Self-confidence/esteem 	<p>Social Awareness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Empathy - Achievement/service orientation - Organizational awareness - Organizational commitment - Leadership
Regulation	<p>Self-Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-control - Trustworthiness - Conscientiousness - Adaptability - Achievement drive - Optimism/<i>Positivism</i> - Initiative - Innovation - Growth Orientation 	<p>Relationship Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing others - Influence - Communication - Conflict management - Positive impact on others - Change catalyst - Building bonds - Teamwork - Collaboration & Cooperation

Sources: Goleman (2002) and Ziv (2014).

Goleman (2002) in a chapter contribution to a book classified the EICs into four groups along with the four major components of emotional intelligence and called them clusters; which further subdivided into twenty five (25) EI competencies while Ziv (2014) in his study later added a competency known as collaboration & cooperation; these twenty six competencies (26) are adapted and related to librarianship for this study as shown in the table above.

The four major components include: Self-awareness, Social awareness, Self-management and Relational management. This model is a refinement of the model Daniel Goleman developed in 1998. Stock (2010) opined that the first three are Intra-personal: they are invisible to others and occur inside of us; the last one is inter-personal: the embedded competencies occur between us and other people and are observable in our behaviour. The author suggests that the better we developed our intra-personal skills, the easier it is to demonstrate our inter-personal skills. It can be observed from the above table that both Self-awareness and Social awareness are Recognition clusters while Self-management and Relational management are Regulatory clusters. Hence for this study, we shall consider each of the clusters in relation to the productivity of librarians in the university library system.

The first component of emotional intelligence is **Emotional self-awareness**. It entails knowing what one feels (Goleman, 2002). This enables an individual to know one's internal states, preferences, resources, and intuitions. It comprises of three self-personal competences which include the following:

a. Emotional self-awareness - The ability to recognize and understand personal moods and emotions and drives, as well as their effect on others. It entails the skill to focus on one's attention on his/her emotional state; knowing one's internal states, preferences, resources and intuitions (Vyas (2005). Also, people who are emotionally self-aware know which emotion they should experience at any given moment. They would recognize the relationship between their own thoughts and feelings and are cognizant of their beliefs, values and goals (Boyatzis, Goleman, & Rhee, 2000).

b. Accurate self-assessment - This is also known as accurate self-evaluation. It entails an ability of knowing one's strengths and limits (Vyas, 2005). It implies how people accurately evaluate themselves and be aware of their strengths, but also recognize and accept their weaknesses (Ziv, 2014). They are open to constant growth and development by learning from their mistakes and experiences, are introspective, and open to constructive feedback and new possibilities. Accurate Self-Assessment was the hallmark of superior performance (Boyatzis, 1982 in Goleman, 2002). "Individuals with the Accurate Self-Assessment competence are aware of their abilities and limitations, seek out feedback and learn from their mistakes, and know where they

need to improve and when to work with others who have complementary strengths” (Goleman, 2002, p.6). Although librarians in the university library are expected to meet some of the information needs of the library users that seek for diverse information from the library collections. The fact remains that he is a human being that is limited in strength, knowledge and even skills. Having this basic knowledge of his limitations, he should not pose himself as having answers to all the library users’ queries but he should refer those difficult queries to other sources (superior officers or resources) that can readily provide answers to their problems. In the same vein, library users should not be over-demanding in their quest for information from the library personnel and its resources; they should take cognizance of the librarians’ limitations.

c. Self-confidence – This is the third competence in the Self-Awareness cluster and it is also known as self-esteem (Ziv, 2014). It entails a strong sense of one's self-worth and capacities (Vyas, 2005). People of this category are self-assured and know their self-worth. They present themselves and their views authentically and powerfully (Ziv, 2014). They respectfully stand up for their views/truths even when doing so is unpopular. They make decisions and follow up with appropriate action. They are open and respectful of others’ opinions even in face of disagreement. It could be generally observed that the level of Self-Confidence was a stronger predictor of workers’ performance in the organization than the level of skill or previous training acquired. In a sixty-year study of more than one thousand high-IQ men and women tracked from early childhood to retirement, those who possessed Self-Confidence during their early years were most successful in their careers (Holahan & Sears, 1995). This implies that people in the librarianship profession are rendering essential services in the society; they are custodians and managers of organized information and knowledge stocked in the library especially in the university library. Aina (2004) asserted that information is needed by everyone in the society both educated and illiterate members of the human society; hence, keepers and organizers of such information occupy a vantage position in any human society especially in the university community and they should be treated as such.

Social awareness is the second component in the emotional intelligence framework. It entails reading people and groups accurately (Goleman, 2002). It comprises of five competencies; these are:

a. Empathy - It means self-awareness; our understanding of others' feelings and concerns flows from awareness of our own feelings (Goleman, 2002). Besides, Ziv (2014) noted that the empathic people are sensitive and understanding of others. They listen effectively, respectfully and attentive to others’ emotional state. It entails the ability to identify with and understand somebody else’s feelings or difficulties. This sensitivity to

others is critical for superior job performance whenever the focus is on interactions with people. Librarians, due to nature of their profession are dealing with diverse information seekers on daily basis; hence, they should be sensitive to the feelings and pains of their library clientele; they should be helpful in alleviating the sufferings of their users while accessing and retrieving the needed information in the library.

b. Achievement/Service orientation - This entails anticipating, recognizing, and meeting customers' needs (Goleman, 2002). It concerns with nurturing relationships with the business customers. This involves setting a positive tone of cooperation no matter how difficult the situation may appear to be and focusing on achieving goals (Stock, 2010). This implies that in the university library, library users are librarians' customers. They are the most important components of any library especially the university library; they are the determinant factor of the library collections. That means without them library cannot operate in vacuum. All the library resources are selected, acquired and processed in relation to the information needs of its users. Hence, librarians should promote good rapport between them and the library users. This could be done by answering their research questions politely, acquiring relevant educational resources that would meet their information needs and rendering other useful services to them without compromising the information policy of the library.

c. Organizational awareness – This is the ability to read the currents of emotions and political realities in groups, is a competence vital to the behind-the-scenes networking and coalition building that allows individuals to wield influence, no matter what their professional role (Ziv, 2014). Insight into group social hierarchies requires Social Awareness on an organizational level, not just an interpersonal one (Vyas, 2005). Goleman (1998) noted that outstanding performers in most organizations share this ability among managers and executive generally, this emotional competence distinguishes star performers. Their ability to read situations objectively, without the distorting lens of their own biases and assumptions, allows them to respond effectively. This implies that in the university library, librarians are expected to be humane when relating with library users but caution needed to be taken here; they must have a working knowledge of the university library information policies, rules and regulations; these must not be compromised for whatever reason while relating with any library user.

d. Organizational commitment – This is aligning with the goals of the group or organization (Vyas, 2005; Goleman, 2002). Organizational commitment can be defined as the degree to which employees believe in and accept organizational goals and desire to remain with the organization (Mathis & Jackson, 2000). It can be generally observed that at the inception of every organization, it has some set of written achievable goals

and objectives which every employee of that organization must believe in it and strictly adhered to all its norms. Employee's failure to do this amounts to a serious offence in the organization. Therefore, it is expected of every librarian to be committed to his/her organization's goals and objectives; nothing should be done to sabotage the overall goals and set objectives of his library or else he will be severely dealt with.

e. Leadership - It entails inspiring and guiding individuals and groups to achieve a stated goal of the organization (Vyas, 2005). Leadership is a "management function, which is mostly directed towards people and social interaction, as well as the process of influencing people so that they will achieve the goals of the organization" (Rizi et al, 2013, p. 7). According to Goleman (2002), leadership style seems to drive organizational performance across a wide span of industries and sectors and appears to be a crucial link in the chain from leader to climate to business success. A study of the heads of forty-two schools in the United Kingdom suggests that leadership style drove up students' academic achievement by directly affecting school climate. When the school head was flexible in leadership style and demonstrated a variety of EI abilities, teachers' attitudes were more positive and students' grades higher; when the leader relied on fewer EI competencies, teachers tended to be demoralized and students underperformed academically (Goleman, 2002, p. 12). Leadership of any organization is an essential factor that determines the success or failure of such institution in the society. Every professional librarian in the university library is a manager and custodian of all the library collections and human resources placed at his disposal. Therefore, it is expect of every librarian to demonstrate some high level of leadership traits that would enable them to efficiently discharge their duties to the library clientele.

Furthermore, **Self-Management** is the third component of the Emotional Intelligence. Self-management refers to managing of internal states, impulses, and resources of the organization in order to achieve a desired goal of the organization (Goleman, 1998). This emotional intelligence cluster consists of eight different competences namely: Self-control; Trustworthiness; Conscientiousness; Adaptability; Achievement drive; Optimism; Initiative and Innovation. These shall be briefly discussed in turn as follows:

a. Self-control/Management – According to Goleman (2002), these manifests largely as the absence of distress and disruptive feelings. Signs of this competence include being unfazed in stressful situations or dealing with a hostile person without lashing out in return. People that manifest this competence do well by regulating and managing their reactions/impulsive feelings/ distressing emotions. They stay collected, centred, focused and positive even in emotionally challenging situations and under

pressure (Ziv, 2014). It can be generally observed that during examination period in any academic library especially in the university library, library work is very stressful and demanding; large number of different categories of readers consult the library collections and facilities for their information needs. So, managing such large volume of readers might be too cumbersome and stressful. At such moment, it is expected of every librarian to have knowledge of their feelings, effectively manage it and know how to manage the positive/negative feelings of this diverse population of readers.

b. Trustworthiness – This entails maintaining standards of honesty and integrity (Vyas, 2005). In a related development, Goleman (2002) asserted that the trustworthiness translates into letting others know one's values and principles, intentions and feelings, and acting in ways that are consistent with them. Daniel Goleman further reiterated that trustworthy individuals are forthright about their own mistakes and confront others about their lapses. A deficit in this ability operates as a career derailer (Goleman, 1998b). Trustworthy people are ethical and are ready to confront unethical behaviour in others; they are consistently reliable in their commitments, accountable for their responsibilities, and keep their promises (Ziv, 2014). Therefore, every librarian is expected to be trustworthy, reliable and dependable in the discharge of his duties in the university library. Librarians in the university library are saddled with the responsibilities of selecting and acquiring educational resources that are relevant in supporting the curricula of various programmes and courses in the university system; hence, they should be trustworthy.

c. Conscientiousness – It refers to taking responsibility for personal performance (Vyas, 2005). The signs of the conscientiousness competence include being careful, self-disciplined, and scrupulous in attending to responsibilities. Conscientiousness distinguishes the model organizational citizens, the people who keep things running as they should. In studies of job performance, outstanding effectiveness in virtually all jobs-from the bottom to the top of the corporate ladder-depends on conscientiousness (Goleman, 2002). Similarly, Ziv (2014) noted that the conscientious individuals are straightforward and authentic in their communication, own their imperfections and the mistakes they make, are planned and organized with their objectives, and stand up strongly for their values and principles in every aspect of their lives. This implies that every librarian in the university is expected to be conscientious. They are to maintain utmost self-discipline in their relationship with different readers especially those female library users and those with questionable characters without soiling their hands (tarnishing their image); thus, they should be men and women of integrity.

d. Adaptability – This refers to flexibility in handling change (Vyas, 2005). Adaptability is the singular competence that our present dispensation calls for in order

to excel (Goleman, 2002). Therefore, superior performers in management ranks exhibit this competence. They are open to new information and can let go of old assumptions and so adapt how they operate. The author further stated that emotional resilience allows an individual to remain comfortable with the anxiety that often accompanies uncertainty and to think "out of the box," displaying on-the-job creativity and applying new ideas to achieve results. Conversely, people who are uncomfortable with risk and change become naysayers who can undermine innovative ideas or be slow to respond to a shift in the marketplace (Goleman, 2002). In a related development, Ziv (2014) posited that people that possess this competence manage changing circumstances effectively, and are adaptable and flexible in how they manage changing priorities and circumstances. This researcher agrees with the assertion of Daniel Goleman who stated that adaptability is a single competence demanded by our present times. This implies that in librarianship, adaptability is one of the essential competences we needed to possess in this era of information explosion.

e. Achievement drive – It refers to striving to improve or meet a standard of excellence (Vyas, 2005). Goleman (1998) noted that David McClelland's landmark work in 1961 "The Achieving Society" established Achievement Orientation as the competence that drives the success of entrepreneurs. Daniel Goleman referred to it as an optimistic striving to continually improve performance. This implies that in the university library sector, librarians are to follow the new trend of ICTs and break forth into new area of processing and disseminating information resources to their clientele.

f. Optimism – This is also known as *Positivism* (Ziv, 2014). It means persistence in pursuing goals despite obstacles and setbacks (Vyas, 2005). Optimism is a key ingredient of achievement because it determines one's reaction to unfavorable events or circumstances; those with high achievement are proactive and persistent, have an optimistic attitude toward setbacks, and operate from hope of success. Studies have shown that optimism can contribute significantly to sales gains, among other accomplishments; they seek opportunities that go beyond what is required or expected of them. Also, they enroll, motivate and support others in the pursuit of a vision, despite set-backs and challenges. They are motivated by what is possible rather than by fear of failure. They face obstacles and set-backs realistically, and move forward from breakdowns or setbacks by intentionally looking for what is possible, rather than looking for who is to blame (Goleman, 2002; Ziv, 2014). This implies that librarians being the managers of all the library resources (manpower and library collections); they execute university library information policies along with other library personnel; hence, they should be optimistic in pursuing the set goals and objectives of the library

and they should not submit to any obstacle that would hinder them from achieving the set goals of their library.

g. Initiative – This refers to readiness to act on opportunities (Vjas, 2005). According to Goleman (2002), those employees in the organization with the initiative competence act before being forced to do so by external events. This means taking anticipatory action to avoid problems before they happen or taking advantage of opportunities before they are visible to anyone else. In the other hand, those individuals who lack Initiative are reactive rather than proactive, lacking the farsightedness that can make the critical difference between a wise decision and a poor one. Initiative is the key to outstanding performance in the university library. This implies that librarians should be proactive while discharging their services to the library users without being forced by any superior authority to do so.

h. Innovation – This entails being comfortable with novel ideas, approaches and new information (Vjas, 2005). Innovative people are original in their ideas and open to new solutions. They risk thinking outside the box and are comfortable straying from what is familiar and acceptable. They handle multiple responsibilities simultaneously. Initiative is key to outstanding performance in industries (Crant, 1995; Rosier, 1996). The researcher concurs with the assertions of these authors. It implies that librarians in the university library should be innovative minded. More importantly, in this era of information explosion; librarians should seek for new and easiest methods through which they can effectively meet the information needs of their clientele. They should not be too rigid in the old and obsolete traditional methods of rendering library services rather; they should have a well-planned career development in the profession and aggressively pursue more innovative courses that would enhance their relevancy and efficiency in this technological based dispensation.

i. Growth orientation – This entails knowledge of continuous expansion/development that an employee has for the organization. It enables workers to be inwardly motivated to grow and achieve desired goals despite challenges and difficulties (Ziv, 2014). Among those five laws of Library Science beautifully proposed by an eminent librarian: S.R. Raganathan in 1963 was that “library is a growing organism”. Library personnel especially the librarians make this possible in the library; they have to formulate and execute actionable policies that would enhance the rapid growth of the library resources; they are to select, acquire and processed all the relevant educational resources that would meet the information needs of all the library users. Thus, every library personnel especially librarians are expected to have growth oriented skill so as to effectively work toward the fast growth of the university library collections

and thereby improve its image among the library users within and outside the university community.

Finally, **Relationship management** is the last component in the emotional intelligence frame work as presented in the above table. It involves inducing desirable responses in others (Goleman, 1998). The relationship management contains set of essential competencies useful developing social skills of workers in the organization. Developing others involves sensing people's developmental needs and bolstering their abilities. The relational management cluster contains nine competencies which shall be discussed in this study as follows:

a. Developing others – This refers to sensing others' development needs and encouraging their abilities (Goleman, 2002; Vjas, 2005). According to Ziv (2014), people that possess this skill support other employees in the organization to grow and thrive by focusing on their strengths and reinforcing their positive aspects rather than focusing on the negatives. They acknowledge and appreciate others for their contribution and conduct. They seek to develop and enhance relationships. They value diversity and differences, viewing them as possibilities (Ziv, 2014). This implies that in the university library, librarians should take delight in mentoring other library personnel so as to encourage them in developing their talents or skills and thereby prepare them for higher responsibility in the organization. There should be a well-designed knowledge management programme in the university library so as to sustain the vital skill of the proficient librarian in case of turnover, retirement or permanent incapability of such experienced staff. Nobody should be an indispensable entity! The university library is a continuous institution in which its operations must not be disturbed by any unforeseen circumstance; thus, other members of library staff must be developed so as to continue its operations.

b. Influence – This refers to possessing power to sway somebody to do one's wish. It entails wielding effective tactics for persuasion (Goleman, 2002; Vjas, 2005; Ziv, 2014). Power to influence is an important skill that every manager in the organization is expected to possess. An average human being has a negative attitude when it comes to work; they have a lukewarm and lazy attitude toward job performance as beautifully articulated by Douglas McGregor in his theories (X and Y), he then assumed that the role of management is to effectively organize resources, including employees, to best benefit the organization. Here, the theorist is emphasizing the role of manager in influencing all the available resources (employees, raw materials and equipment) in the organization toward achieving its stated goals. This implies that in the university library, librarians are expected to actively influence other library personnel in achieving the set goals of the library within and outside the university community.

c. Communication – This entails listening openly and sending convincing messages to other people (Goleman, 2002; Vyas, 2005). It refers to exchange of information between two or more people in the organization, e.g. by means of speaking, writing or body language or by common system of signs or behaviour (culled from the system dictionary). Communication is an essential competence needed to promote evenly development in any organization; this implies that communication is an essential tool that enhances speedy and effective achievement of the organizational stated goals and set objectives. The university library is a service delivery institution that needs effective communication among its personnel, resources and users. It means for any library collection to be found useful to the library users, it has to be effectively communicated in term of selecting relevant resources, systematically organizing and displaying or disseminating such materials to its readers. In all these processes, communication (oral, writing or signs) takes place before users can find them useful for their information needs.

In the same vein, active communication is an important ingredient among the library personnel. Every university library has some stated goals and set objectives to be achieved to its users and to its immediate community; these have to be effectively communicated to all the library staff as this enhances their understanding of such goals before they can be successfully implemented. Hence, communication should be regular and constant among the university library collections, personnel and users.

d. Conflict management – This entails negotiating and resolving disagreements between two or more people in the organization (Goleman, 2002; Vjas, 2005). Conflict resolution competence is an important skill that every manager in any human organization especially in the university library should possess. Conflict is an inevitable occurrence in any human society; it can happen or take place between two or more people within a group of individuals at any time and for any reason; hence, it has to be settled amicably in order to promote peaceful work environment that our human society needed for the expected development.

People that possess this skill effectively focus on identifying positive solutions rather than staying stuck on who is “right” or who is “wrong.” They are open to dialogue and discussion and are authentic and effective in communication. Also, they are straightforward and open to feedback, respectful listeners, and take responsibility for contributing to both the creation of a breakdown, as well as to arriving at an optimal resolution of any such breakdown (Ziv, 2014). Although, university library is not an arbitrary court of law where human differences are expected to be amicably settled; yet, it is a service delivery institution where diverse population of readers converged on daily basis for their information needs. Offences must definitely take place among these

users due to their different background/cultural settings and diversity of information interest. Thus, librarians are to serve as arbiters among these library users so as to promote the serenity that every library deserves.

e. Positive impact on others – This entails a situation where an individual has a strong effect on the behaviour of another person or group of people in the organization or in the entire human society. Ziv (2014) believed that these types of people are able to help other people in the organization to see the big picture and influence them in seeking out desired positive outcomes while adhering to ethical values and principles. The university library as aforementioned in this study plays host to different categories of users from different cultural settings on daily basis and these users are not having similar characters; while some of them have very sound home trainings which make them to behave maturely; others are not so fortunate to have such upbringings, some even come from broken homes. What do you expect from such readers? The negative and aggressive behaviours that would be displayed by such library user may not be too pleasant to everyone in the library. Thus, librarians are expected to take up the role of managing such readers and make a positive impact on them through constant counselling and enduring the negative behaviour of such readers.

f. Change catalyst – According to Vjas (2005) and Goleman (2002), this entails initiating or managing change in the organization. As earlier mentioned in this study, in every human society or organization people's characters differ; while some are positively minded others are having negative and bad behaviour. In any situation, managers are expected to manage everyone in order to achieve the organizational goals and objectives. People who possess this type of emotional skill are oriented toward identifying the positive aspects of a person or a situation. They take the initiative in identifying the change necessary toward the achievement of positive/desired outcomes (Ziv, 2014). This researcher concurs with the view of Talia Ziv; in the university library, librarians are to be instrumental in bringing positive change in all the library users.

g. Building bonds – This refers to nurturing instrumental relationships (Vjas, 2005). In support of Kartik Vjas' submission, Stock (2010) opined that managers should nurture good relationships among employees in the organization. They should have ability to demonstrate sincere care (as contrasted with "required courtesy") for others. They build on strengths and avoid blaming, judging, criticizing and pointing accusing fingers (Ziv, 2014). This can be done through word and deed, demonstrate appreciation for people's efforts and contribution. The author further stressed that this is about setting a positive tone of cooperation no matter how difficult the situation or conversation and having other's best interests in mind while focusing on achieving set goals of the organization. This implies that in the university library, librarians should

possess the emotional skill of nurturing positive relationships among diverse populations of library users; they should be able to resolve some minor differences among library users without pointing accusing fingers on anyone but every matter should be amicably settled among the feuding parties.

h. Teamwork – It refers to team capabilities towards creating group synergy in pursuing collective goals of the organization (Goleman, 2002; Vjas, 2005). Teamwork is an essential competence that enhances the survival and continuous existence of any organization. At the inception of every organization, there are some stated goals and objectives which the authority of such organization expected its employees to accomplish within a stipulated period of time. These set goals are to be realized through the team capabilities of every worker in the organization; that is, every individual worker in the organization is to form a group of synergy and collectively pursue the stated goals of their organization. This implies that in the university library, teamwork of library staff is very important for the realization of the library set goals. University library personnel consist of three categories of staff: professional librarians, para-professional staff (library officer cadres) and the supportive staff (library assistants, secretaries, computer operators; etc.). These groups of various library workers are to work together as a unified entity towards the achievement of the university library goals; it is a serious offence for any member of the library personnel to do otherwise; such fallible staff will be heavily sanctioned by the authority. Hence, every library personnel should work together as a force in achieving the common goals of the library.

Finally, **Collaboration competence** – It refers to working with others towards shared goals. It can also be seen as cooperation with other groups of individuals or bodies for the attainment of organizational goals (Goleman, 2002; Vjas, 2005). It can be generally observed that no organization is financially and materially strong enough to be self-sustained; every organization depends on one another for their sustained growth and development. This implies that libraries in general have to collaborate and cooperate with one another for the provision of all the relevant information resources needed by their users. That means, no library not even the largest library in the world could boast of having enough educational materials needed by their readers; hence, they have to collaborate and cooperate with other similar libraries within and outside their locations to do so.

However, some similar libraries can put their financial resources together in order to acquire relevant library resources and share such acquired materials based on the ratio of their contributions. This type of library collaboration is known as consortium building of educational materials (Adeyokun & Yaya, 2010). The authors believed that this method enhances the capital base of the participating libraries and it

enables those smaller libraries to have large volumes of educational materials in their library stocks. The researcher concurs with the submission of these authors; collaboration and cooperation that take place among the participatory libraries so as to enhance the productivity of librarians in such library; therefore, librarians have enough library resources at their disposal to meet the information needs of their users. Consequently, it is expected of every librarian in the university library to possess collaboration and cooperation skills in order to increase their level of job performance.

4. Theoretical Framework

4.1 Daniel Goleman Emotional Intelligence Theory

	Self	Social
	Self-Awareness	Social-Awareness
Recognition	<u>Self-confidence</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emotional self-awareness Accurate self- assessment 	<u>Empathy</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organizational awareness Understanding the environment
Regulation	Self-Management <u>Self-control</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trustworthiness Conscientiousness Adaptability Drive and motivation Initiative 	Relationship Management <u>Influence</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inspirational leadership Developing others Influence Conflict management Building bonds Teamwork & Collaboration

Figure 1: Daniel Goleman Showing 26 EI Competencies

Source: Goleman (1998)

The theory was propounded by Daniel Goleman in 1998, in his book Working with Emotional Intelligence and clarified in a later article (Goleman, 2001); he sets out a framework of emotional intelligence (EI) that reflects how an individual’s potential for mastering the skills of Self-Awareness, Self-Management, Social-Awareness, and Relationship Management translates into on-the-job success. The theory is about having ability to understand and manage emotion of yourself and also those around you in the organization and in the entire human society.

The theory is related to emotional intelligence variable of the study. Daniel Goleman, a psychologist and originator of the theory stressed that emotional

intelligence competencies are job skills that can, and indeed must, be learned (Goleman, 1998). Daniel Goleman through the theory made the idea of EI popular and acceptable in the management circle presented the concept of emotional intelligence as being encapsulated by the following four elements shown in the above framework. The researcher adopts this theory for the study.

Self-Awareness - The first element of Emotional Intelligence theory – Being self-aware means that you understand yourself – You understand what makes you tick (happy) and therefore, your strengths and weaknesses as a person and as a leader or (manager of people in the organization). You can then start to understand why you feel, and what makes you feel. Daniel Goleman states that if you understand your emotions, you can identify their impact to you and those in your team. It is a path on the road to having humility, which is much needed facet in leadership.

Self-Management - The second element of Goleman's Emotional Intelligence – Through being in control of what you say and do whilst rejecting the temptation to make rushed decisions, you can be in charge of your action and therefore reducing the chances of compromising your values. Other aspects to nurture in this element are to show and actively apply conscientiousness, trustworthiness, leading and adapting to change, complete drive to succeed and the initiative to think fast and act creatively and innovatively solve problems in life and in the organization.

Social-Awareness - The third element in Goleman's EI theory – Social-Awareness is the ability for a leader to understand the emotions of the team members around them and to get good comprehension of their emotional makeup. The ability to treat people according to these emotional reactions is vital (for the success and growth of any organization). This area is linked to empathy: The ability to understand and see things in other people's viewpoints (perspective), expertise in building and retaining talent, valuing diversity and appreciating the organizational goals.

Relationship management - The fourth and final Goleman's Emotional Intelligence theory. It enables an individual to relate excellently well with other people. It is otherwise known as social skill which links leadership and emotional intelligence together. Leaders (or librarians) with good social skills are often very good communicators (and they are very good job performers at workplace). Leaders or managers who good in this skill or competence are also good at conflict resolution and communicating the visions to team members, enlightening them and creating motivation and inspiration throughout the team. They are experts in getting their team to support them and also believe in their leadership. They set the example for other people to follow by demonstrating the acceptable behaviour and values. Although this theory is widely consulted and accepted globally, yet it has been heavily criticised by

some scholars arguing that some vital competencies that would enhance organizational success are missing or mixed up in Goleman’s 1998 framework. To solve this problem, Daniel Goleman updated the 1998 framework in 2002.

However, from the above theory of Emotional Intelligence, it was discovered that: Emotional Intelligence (EI) is a powerful force during human creativity and interests (Akinboye, 2003). Thus, leading to great prospects for education, librarianship, family life, career development and so on; emotional Intelligence has proved to be a better predictor of future success for the organization; and performance is used to label the observable manifestation of knowledge, skills, concepts and understanding and ideas (Yaya, 2007)

The major impact that this theory has on the study is that it helps librarians in the university library to monitor or control their feelings and emotions at the moment of challenging situation around them; they will use the knowledge gathered to guide their thinking and actions in dealing or relating with various people that visit the library for their information needs and this would eventually enhance their success as information providers in the university community.

Besides, a librarian who possesses the emotional intelligence skills like empathy, recognition of other employees feelings among others as pointed out in this study; and develop strategies in motivating workforce that are under his or her leadership will achieve higher level of job satisfaction and productivity than his counterparts that possess less degree of emotional intelligence leadership skills. This affirmed the study of Swanson and Zobisch (2014) who posited that EI has proved to be an effective skill leading to an individual’s overall success in the workplace.

4.2 Conceptual Model for the Study

Figure 2: Conceptual model for the Study

Source: Yaya (2016)

4.3 Discussion of the Conceptual Model

The conceptual framework for this study is built on the theories and literatures reviewed. The model is broadly divided into two parts: Independent and Dependent variables. The independent variable compartment consists of Emotional intelligence, while the dependent variable box houses Productivity of librarians in the university library. It can be observed from the literatures reviewed that several factors affect the emotional intelligence of workers and therefore their levels of productivity.

Emotional intelligence box consists of four components: self-awareness, self-management, social-awareness and relationship management. Each of these components contains some number of emotional intelligence competencies that are expected of every employee to possess in order to be more effective while discharging their duties in the organization. Therefore, twenty six emotional intelligence competencies are adapted from Goleman (1998), Goleman (2002) and Ziv (2014), and discussed in relationship to productivity of librarians. It is imperative for every librarian to have full knowledge of his or her emotion, know how to manage it and that of other people (library clientele and colleagues) in order to render effective services to the information seekers.

This knowledge as confirmed by Goleman (1995); Azuka and Kurumeh (2015) are not innate talents, but rather learned capabilities could be obtained through education, training and career development at school, conferences, workshops, seminars and at workplace. They must be worked on and developed to achieve outstanding performance at workplace.

5. Methodology

5.1 Research Design

The correlational research design was adopted for this study. According to Cheng (2016), correlational research design could be used to describe the relationship between two or more variables, as well as how strongly these variables relates to one another. In other words, it aims to determine the relationship between two or more variables and the strength of this relationship.

In the same vein, Kowalczyk (2015) posited that the whole purpose of using correlations in research is to figure out which variables are connected. The researcher concurs with these authors' assertions. Thus, correlational research design was adopted for this study in order to establish the relationships between the variables.

5.2 Population

The population for this study consisted of 1,254 librarians from the 81 public universities (Federal & State) in Nigeria. The list comprised of 41 Federal universities and 40 State owned universities. The four which have not taken off at the time of conducting this study were excluded. Each geopolitical zone has the following records of university libraries and librarians: North-Central (including Federal Capital Territory) has 13 university libraries with 244 librarians; North-East has 11 university libraries with 128 librarians; North-West has 16 university libraries with 272 librarians; South-East has 10 university libraries with 167 librarians; South-South has 13 university libraries with 203 librarians; and South West has 15 university libraries with 240 librarians. Thus, all the university libraries and their librarians are potential respondents of this study.

5.3 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The sample size for this study is 923 librarians. Random sampling technique was adopted for this study. The sampling was done by first stratifying the country (Nigeria) along the existing six geopolitical zones (strata); these include: North-Central, North-East, North-West, South-East, South-South and South-West. Each zone (stratum) is made up of six States except North-West and South East that are made up of seven and five States respectively.

Consequently, the researcher surveyed all the librarians in all the public university libraries established in the four selected geopolitical zones and states. The selected zones and states were listed as follow: North-Central (Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Plateau and Federal Capital Territory); North-West (Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Jigawa, Sokoto and Zamfara); South-East (Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo); and South-West (Ekiti, Lagos, Ogun, Ondo, Osun and Oyo). The choice of these states was to give a wider coverage of all the professional librarians working in all public (federal & state) universities sited in each state of the geopolitical zones selected for the study. Also, each state has public universities to be surveyed, similar cultural and economic activities, as well as similar religious settings.

The researcher randomly selected 60% sample size from the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria which give approximately four zones; these included: North-Central, North-West, South-East and South-West. According to Nachimias and Nachimias (1987), the rate between 50-75% of sample size were considered acceptable in research; hence, the choice of 60% of the geopolitical zones in the country was to give fair representation of the entire country (two geopolitical zones were selected from each part of the country i.e. North & South) as all the geopolitical zones in Nigeria might be too large and

cumbersome to handle within the stipulated time frame. Also, to enable the researcher complete the study within the limited resources available for the study.

Besides, each of the geopolitical zones selected for the study has the following records of university libraries and librarians: North-Central has 13 university libraries with 244 librarians; North-West has 16 university libraries with 272 librarians; South-East has 10 university libraries with 167 librarians; and South-West has 15 university libraries with 240 librarians. The number of librarians in the fifty four (54) selected public university libraries considered for this study was calculated at 923.

5.4 Research Instrument

The researcher employed the questionnaire in collecting data for this study. The questionnaire for this study was designed by the researcher and was designed along the identified research questions. Hence, the research instrument was divided into four sections: A, B, C and D. Items in the instrument were gathered from the literature reviewed for the study. **Section A:** Demographic information; **section B:** Level of Productivity; **section C:** Level of emotional intelligence; and **section D:** Challenging issues that affect productivity of librarians in the university library.

5.5 Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The research instrument was subjected to the scrutiny of the researcher's supervisors, some university librarians especially those with PhD degree in the field of librarianship and other experts in the areas of the variables studied; these were approached for their useful advice and input in order to validate the research instrument used for the study. Both face and content validity were employed in order to standardise the instrument and to make it more adequate for the study. Based on their useful feedback, the research instrument was modified where necessary.

Also, a pilot study was conducted. The researcher through friends and research assistants administered 56 questionnaires and retrieved 38 copies (67.9%); among professional librarians of three public university libraries that were not part of the sample for the main study, these included: University of Benin, Delta State University and Ambrose Alli University all in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. These were subjected to Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis and with alpha reliability coefficient results as follows: Emotional Intelligence of Librarians $\alpha = 0.91$ and Productivity of Librarians had $\alpha = 0.94$. With these results, the instrument was used for the study as the alpha reliability coefficient results for all the variables are more than 0.5 level of significant.

5.6 Research Procedure and Method of Data Collection

The corrected copies of the questionnaire were administered to professional librarians in all the fifty four (54) university libraries slated for the study. The respondents were assured that information supplied by them would be treated with utmost confidentiality and used solely for the purposes of academic research. Also, such information will not be divulged to a third party. The researcher intended to personally administer copies of the questionnaire to the affected librarians; but due to the wide geographical zones to be covered for the study and limited time frame, the researcher engaged the services of research assistants, electronic administration of the instrument to most of the respondents, friends working in most of these university libraries, NLA online forum and even the University Librarians so as to add credibility to the data collected and analysed for the study. On the whole, 923 copies of the corrected questionnaire were administered to librarians in all the 54 public university libraries slated for the study; out of which, a total number of 620 copies were retrieved. This gives 67.2% return rate of the administered research instrument for the study.

5.7 Method of Data Analysis

Data collected for this study was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS), 22.0 latest versions. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics, especially for research questions 1-3, while the null hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis. The result was to attest to the mutual relationship that existed among the variables (Emotional intelligence and Productivity) in the study.

6. Data Analysis Results and Discussion of Findings

6.1 Presentation of Demographic Information of Respondents

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of respondents

S/N	DEMOGRAPHIC STATEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1.	Gender		
	Male	353	56.9
	Female	267	43.1
	Total	620	100.0
2.	Marital status		
	Single	114	18.4
	Married	455	73.4
	Divorced	33	5.3

Japheth Abdulazeez Yaya, Oluseyi A. Akintayo, Chioma Euriel Uzohue –
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND PRODUCTIVITY OF LIBRARIANS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN
NIGERIA: A CORRELATIONAL APPROACH

	Widowed	18	2.9
	Total	620	100.0
3.	Age of respondents		
	Below 30	105	16.9
	31-40	186	30.0
	41-50	206	33.2
	51-60	116	18.7
	Above 60	7	1.1
	Total	620	100.0
4.	Educational qualification		
	BSc/BA	92	14.9
	BLIS	128	20.6
	MSc/MA	49	7.9
	MLIS	312	50.3
	PhD	39	6.3
	Total	620	100.0
5.	Designation		
	Assistant Librarian	170	27.4
	Librarian II	133	21.5
	Librarian I	133	21.5
	Senior Librarian	81	13.1
	Principal Librarian	64	10.3
	Deputy University Librarian	27	4.4
	University Librarian	12	1.9
	Total	620	100.0
6.	Length of service		
	Below 6 years	213	34.4
	6-10 years	156	25.2
	11-15 years	108	17.4
	16-20years	52	8.4
	21-25 years	23	3.7
	26-30 years	54	8.7
	Above 30 years	14	2.3
	Total	620	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2016

From Table 1, it reveals that (56.9%) of the respondents were male. This implied that there were slightly more men in the librarianship profession than women in Nigeria. It was also revealed that majority of the respondents were married (73.4%). This implies that they would display maturity while discharging their duties to the library users in their various universities. It was revealed that there were more librarians in the age bracket of 41-50 years than any other age group closely followed by those in the age

bracket 31-40. This simply meant a larger percentage of the respondents were relatively young and active.

Pertaining to the educational qualifications of the respondents, 50.3% were holders of Master’s Degree in Library Science (MLIS) and others 20.6% were holders of Bachelor Degree in Library Science. This means that at least 71% of respondents were professionally qualified librarians. If it is assumed that the 6% who had Ph.D degrees got them from the field of librarianship, then this figure will increase to 77%. This shows that about a quarter (23%) of people working in Nigerian university libraries today hold degrees outside librarianship. This is understandable considering the role that information technology is playing in today’s information provision services.

It was revealed from the table that 70% of librarians in Nigerian universities occupied the low level positions (Assistant Librarians, Librarian II, Librarian I) in the library. Assistant Librarians constituted the largest number in this group. Almost 80% of the respondents had spent less than 15 years as Librarians or Assistant Librarians, while almost half (34.4%) had spent less than 6 years. Those that had spent over 20 years on the job amounted to only 15% of respondents.

6.2 Data Analysis and Presentation Based on Research Questions

Research Question 1: *What is the level of productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria?*

Table 2: Level of productivity of the respondents

S/N	STATEMENT	VH (%)	H (%)	M (%)	L (%)	Mean	SD	AM
a.	Students’ academic success							
i.	Library collection enhances academic success of students in the university	411 (66.3)	181 (29.2)	26 (4.2)	2 (0.3)	3.64	0.540	3.56
ii.	Library provides conducive learning environment that encourages academic success	376 (60.6)	211 (34)	29 (4.7)	4 (0.8)	3.61	0.584	
iii.	With current and relevant library collections, students will excel in their academic programmes	323 (52.1)	260 (41.9)	32 (5.2)	5 (0.8)	3.55	0.617	
iv.	My job performance often lead to students’ success in their examinations	356 (57.4)	221 (35.6)	38 (6.1)	5 (0.8)	3.45	0.633	
b.	Accreditation of more courses							
i.	My job performance contribute greatly to the accreditation exercises of the	394 (63.5)	194 (31.3)	28 (4.5)	4 (0.6)	3.58	0.611	

Japheth Abdulazeez Yaya, Oluseyi A. Akintayo, Chioma Euriel Uzohue –
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND PRODUCTIVITY OF LIBRARIANS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN
NIGERIA: A CORRELATIONAL APPROACH

	university							
ii.	I actively involved in the accreditation exercises	390 (62.9)	203 (32.7)	22 (3.5)	5 (0.8)	3.58	0.603	3.55
iii.	Relevant and current library collections help the university authority to have more courses accredited	385 (62.1)	189 (30.5)	40 (6.5)	6 (1)	3.54	0.661	
iv.	It encourages growth and development of the university	367 (59.2)	224 (36.1)	22 (3.5)	7 (1.1)	3.53	0.623	
v.	It enriches the university curricula and programmes.	356 (57.4)	221 (35.6)	38 (6.1)	5 (0.8)	3.50	0.649	
c.	Innovative research work							
i.	It provides resources for innovative research work.	362 (58.4)	226 (36.5)	27 (4.4)	5 (0.8)	3.52	0.621	3.51
ii.	My job output greatly contribute to the innovative research efforts of the university community	346 (55.8)	252 (40.6)	18 (2.9)	4 (0.6)	3.52	0.589	
iii.	It promotes the image of the university.	351 (56.6)	241 (38.9)	24 (3.9)	4 (0.6)	3.51	0.605	
iv.	My job performance contributes to innovative research work in the university.	369 (59.5)	205 (33.1)	35 (5.6)	11 (1.8)	3.50	0.686	
d.	Increase number of paper publication							
i.	Library collection boosts regular paper publications of faculty members.	436 (70.3)	156 (25.2)	25 (4)	3 (0.5)	3.61	0.550	3.39
ii.	It provides resources for regular paper publications	330 (53.2%)	256 (41.3)	30 (4.8)	4 (0.6)	3.47	0.621	
iii.	My regular paper publications assures me of promotion as at when due	331 (53.4)	248 (40)	31 (5)	10 (1.6)	3.45	0.667	
iv.	Three of my publications are in international journals	335 (54)	176 (28.4)	70 (11.3)	39 (6.3)	3.30	0.903	
v.	It enhances my regular paper publications.	395 (63.7)	180 (29)	36 (5.8)	9 (1.5)	3.26	0.989	
vi.	I have produced at least five papers in the past two years	305 (49.2)	202 (32.6)	82 (13.2)	31 (5)	3.26	0.871	

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Key: VH = Very High, H = High, M = Medium, L = Low, SD = Standard Deviation; AM = Average Mean

It can be seen from Table 2 that librarians in Nigerian Universities considered their level of productivity to be very high judging by the average mean score of 3.39 on the scale of 4. They considered their contribution to the academic success of students as well as the universities' success in getting more courses accredited as the greatest measures of their productivity in the university system. Each had an average mean scores of 3.56 and 3.55

respectively. Specifically, having the relevant library collections (mean = 3.64) and conducive reading and learning environment contribute to students' academic success while active involvement in accreditation activities (mean = 3.58) plus having the right collection (mean = 3.58) contributed to the increase in the number of courses accredited.

Other activities of librarians' productivity were their contribution to innovative research work in the university (average mean = 3.51) and increase in the number of papers published by them (average mean = 3.39). Specifically, providing resources for innovative research work (mean = 3.52) coupled with having relevant collections to boost paper publications of faculty members (mean = 3.61) in the university system.

Research Question 2: *What is the level of emotional intelligence of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria?*

Table 3: Level of emotional intelligence and productivity of the respondents

S/N	STATEMENT	VGE (%)	GE (%)	ME (%)	NE (%)	MEAN	SD	AM
a.	Relationship management							
i.	Positive impact on others	367 (59.2)	205 (33.1)	36 (5.8)	12 (1.9)	3.50	0.695	3.44
ii.	Collaboration and cooperation	339 (54.7)	258 (41.6)	11 (1.8)	12 (1.9)	3.49	0.634	
iii.	Conflict management	348 (56.1)	220 (35.5)	51 (8.2)	1 (0.2)	3.48	0.651	
iv.	Communication	343 (55.3)	243 (39.2)	25 (4)	9 (1.5)	3.48	0.647	
v.	Building bonds	329 (53.1)	253 (40.8)	34 (5.5)	4 (0.6)	3.46	0.631	
vi.	Influence i.e. Influencing others	337 (54.4)	226 (36.5)	40 (6.5)	17 (2.7)	3.42	0.734	
vii.	Developing others	331 (53.4)	216 (34.8)	61 (9.8)	12 (1.9)	3.40	0.744	
viii.	Change catalyst	312 (50.3)	245 (39.5)	52 (8.4)	11 (1.8)	3.38	0.715	
ix.	Teamwork	298 (48.1)	245 (39.5)	71 (11.5)	6 (1)	3.35	0.717	
b.	Self-awareness							
i.	Self-confidence/esteem	341 (55)	242 (39)	25 (4)	12 (1.9)	3.47	0.668	3.42
ii.	Accurate self-assessment/evaluation	356 (57.4)	195 (31.5)	56 (9)	13 (2.1)	3.44	0.744	
iii.	Emotional self-awareness	324	210	65	21	3.35	0.801	

Japheth Abdulazeez Yaya, Oluseyi A. Akintayo, Chioma Euriel Uzohue –
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND PRODUCTIVITY OF LIBRARIANS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN
NIGERIA: A CORRELATIONAL APPROACH

		(52.3)	(33.9)	(10.5)	(3.4)			
c.	Self-management							
i.	Growth orientation	328 (52.9)	259 (41.8)	28 (4.5)	5 (0.8)	3.47	0.623	3.42
ii.	Innovation	349 (56.8)	221 (35.6)	32 (5.2)	18 (2.9)	3.45	0.725	
iii.	Trustworthiness	343 (55.3)	231 (37.3)	26 (4.2)	20 (3.2)	3.45	0.725	
iv.	Optimism/positivism	340 (54.8)	219 (35.3)	56 (9)	5 (0.8)	3.44	0.690	
v	Initiative	335 (54)	224 (36.1)	52 (8.4)	9 (1.5)	3.43	0.707	
vi.	Conscientiousness	325 (52.4)	226 (36.5)	55 (8.9)	14 (2.3)	3.39	0.743	
vii.	Self-control	332 (53.5)	213 (34.4)	60 (9.7)	15 (2.4)	3.39	0.740	
viii.	Adaptability	308 (49.7)	262 (42.3)	35 (5.6)	15 (2.4)	3.39	0.705	
ix.	Achievement drive	302 (48.7)	247 (39.8)	59 (9.5)	12 (1.9)	3.35	0.732	
d..	Social-awareness							
v.	Leadership	300 (48.4)	272 (43.9)	46 (7.4)	2 (0.3)	3.40	0.640	3.32
vi.	Empathy	276 (44.5)	293 (47.3)	45 (7.3)	6 (1)	3.35	0.658	
vii.	Organizational commitment	278 (44.8)	276 (44.5)	60 (9.7)	6 (1)	3.33	0.689	
viii.	Achievement/service orientation	278 (44.8)	269 (43.4)	66 (10.6)	7 (1.1)	3.32	0.706	
ix.	Organizational awareness	247 (39.8)	281 (45.3)	66 (10.6)	26 (4.2)	3.21	0.794	

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Key: VGE = Very Great Extent; GE = Great Extent; ME = Moderate Extent; NE = No Extent; SD = Standard Deviation; AM = Average Mean

Table 3 shows that librarians in Nigerian Universities considered their level of emotional intelligence to be very high judging by the average mean score of 3.32 on the scale of 4. They considered their relational management of the library users as well as their self-awareness ability as the greatest measures of their emotional intelligence in the university system. Each had an average mean scores of 3.44 and 3.42 respectively. Specifically, having ability to make positive impact on others especially university students (mean = 3.50) followed by their collaboration and cooperation (mean = 3.49)

with others especially with similar academic libraries in meeting the information needs of library users while self-confidence/esteem (mean = 3.47) plus having the accurate self-assessment or evaluation (mean = 3.44) contributed to increase in their productivity in the university library.

Other emotional intelligence components related to librarians' productivity were their self-management in the university (average mean = 3.42) and their social-awareness of the university (average mean = 3.32). Specifically, having growth orientation to increase the library collections (mean = 3.47) coupled with their innovation (mean = 3.45) skills to introduce new dimensions to improve service delivery efforts of the university library.

Research Question 3: *What challenges face librarians' productivity in public university libraries in Nigeria?*

Table 4.7: Challenging issues affecting productivity of librarians

S/N	STATEMENT	VGE(%)	GE(%)	ME(%)	NE(%)	M	SD	AM
i.	Non-payment of similar allowances payable to other academic staff in the university	264(42.6)	209(33.7)	85(13.7)	62(10)	3.09	0.978	
ii.	Lack of employee recognition	273(44)	192(31)	88(14.2)	67(10.8)	3.08	1.005	3.02
iii.	Marginalization of librarians by the university authority.	266(42.9)	190(30.6)	85(13.7)	79(12.7)	3.04	1.037	
iv.	Irregular payment of salary and wages	269(43.4)	172(27.7)	107(17.3)	72(11.6)	3.03	1.035	
v.	Lack of conducive work environment in my university	256(41.3)	194(31.3)	101(16.3)	69(11.1)	3.03	1.011	
vi.	Irregular promotion opportunities	237(38.2)	221(35.6)	93(15)	69(11.1)	3.01	0.989	
vii.	Lack of effective job design that would enable library services to be effectively carried out	250(40.3)	200(32.3)	96(15.5)	74(11.9)	3.01	1.018	
viii.	Inadequate provision for my basic needs by the organization	218(35.2)	236(38.1)	111(17.9)	55(8.9)	3.00	0.942	
ix.	Inadequate security of lives and library resources	221(35.6)	248(40)	65(10.5)	86(13.9)	2.97	1.009	
x.	Undemocratic leadership styles in my library	236(38.4)	196(31.6)	114(18.4)	74(11.9)	2.96	1.021	

Source: Survey Field, 2016

Key: VGE = Very Great Extent; GE = Great Extent; ME = Moderate Extent; NE = Not Extent; M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; AM = Average Mean

Table 4 reveals that librarians in Nigerian Universities considered those issues affecting librarians' job satisfaction and productivity to be high judging by the average mean score of 3.02 on the scale of 4. Major challenging issues facing Nigerian university librarians were non-payment of similar allowances payable to other academic staff (mean = 3.09), lack of employee recognition (mean = 3.08) and marginalization of librarians by the university authorities (mean = 3.04), irregular payment of salary and wages (mean = 3.03), lack of conducive work environment (mean = 3.03).

Others were irregular promotion opportunities (mean = 3.01), lack of effective job design (mean = 3.01), inadequate provision of basic needs to librarians (mean = 3.00), inadequate security of lives and properties (mean = 2.97) as well as undemocratic leadership styles (mean = 2.96).

6.3 Hypotheses Testing and Interpretation

Ho: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis between Emotional Intelligence and Productivity of Librarians in Public University Libraries in Nigeria

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	N	R	P	Remark
Emotional Intelligence	3.21	0.79	620	0.032	0.000	Sig.
Productivity	3.55	0.67				

Significant at 0.05 level

The mean score of the emotional intelligence of librarians in Nigerian university libraries was 3.21, SD = 0.79 while that of productivity was 3.55, SD = 0.67. The correlation of coefficient obtained was 0.032 with p-value < 0.05. The result showed positive correlation between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians. There was a positive significant relationship between the variables as indicated in the above table as ($r = 0.032$, $N = 620$, $P < 0.05$). Null hypothesis five is rejected. This indicates that there is significant relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria.

6.4 Discussion of Findings

This section discussed the major findings of this study in relation to past studies. The discussion followed the research questions on which sources of relationships between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians were established through past empirical studies. Each of the three research questions and the null hypothesis were

based on determining the influence emotional intelligence had on the productivity of librarians.

Research question one showed that librarians' contribution to the academic success of students as well as the universities' success in getting more courses accredited as the greatest measures of their productivity in the university system. The findings implied that library was fundamental to research productivity and that it supported the curricula of the universities. These were consistent with the research conducted by Okonedo et al (2015) in which the research productivity of various academic staff in the university was found relatively high in order to assure their chances of being promoted to the next position. It was revealed in the study that librarians' job performance often lead to students' academic success in their examinations; library provided students with current and relevant library collections and these help students to excel in their various academic programmes. Also, library equally provided conducive and quiet learning environment that encouraged users' personal reading and students' academic success as its collections enhanced academic success of students in the university.

Besides, librarians were actively involved in the accreditation exercises; as well as enriching the curricula of both old and new programmes that were offered. This encouraged growth and development of the university. Periodically, every university in Nigeria sought for approval of Nigerian Universities Commission (NUC) before the commencement of any new programme; to facilitate this, library must be well stocked with relevant and current educational resources that would support such programme. In absence of this, no university programme will be accredited by the government statutory organization – NUC. This concurred with the study of Singh and Jain(2013) who listed accreditation of courses in the university as part of the factors through which an employee could derive job satisfaction and this would enhance the level of his/her productivity.

Research question two showed that librarians considered their relational management of the library users as well as their self-awareness ability as the greatest measures of their emotional intelligence in the university system. Specifically, having ability to make positive impact on others especially university students (mean = 3.50) followed by their collaboration and cooperation (mean = 3.49) with others especially with similar academic libraries in meeting the information needs of library users.

It was revealed by the respondents that librarians were to make positive impact on other people especially library users, in which students constituted highest number in the university system. This result agreed with the position of Ziv (2014), who noted that, an individual who has a strong effect on the behaviour of another person or group

of people in the organization or in the entire human society. He believed that these types of people were able to help other people in the organization to see the big picture and influenced them in seeking out desired positive outcomes while adhering to ethical values and principles.

The researcher agreed with Ziv's submission, it implied that the university library played host to different categories of users from different cultural settings on daily basis and these users were not having similar characters; while some of them had very sound home trainings which made them to behave maturely; others were not so fortunate to have such upbringings, some even came from broken homes. What do you expect from such readers? The negative and aggressive behaviours that would be displayed by such library user may not be too pleasant to everyone in the library. Thus, librarians were expected to take up the role of managing such readers and make a positive impact on them through constant counselling and enduring the negative behaviour of such readers. Although they were also expected to be humane when relating with library users but caution needed to be taken here; they must have a working knowledge of the university library information policies, rules and regulations; these must not be compromised for whatever reason while relating with or trying to make positive impact on any library user.

Besides, collaboration and cooperation, the findings corroborated with the submission of Adeyokun and Yaya (2010) that library should not be operated as an island or in isolation rather it should have working relationship with other similar libraries. They can put their financial resources together in order to acquire relevant library resources and share such acquired materials based on the ratio of their contributions. This type of library collaboration is known as consortium building of educational materials. The authors believed that this method enhances the capital base of the participating libraries and it enables those smaller libraries to have large volumes of educational materials in their library stocks. The researcher concurs with the submission of these authors; collaboration and cooperation should take place among the participatory libraries so as to enhance the productivity of librarians in such library; therefore, librarians would have enough library resources at their disposal to meet the information needs of their users. Consequently, it is expected of every librarian in the university library to possess collaboration and cooperation skills in order to increase their level of job performance.

The findings also revealed self-awareness competency contributed immensely to the service delivery efforts of librarians in the university system. It is expected of every librarian to possess self-confidence competency while discharging their duties in the university library. The result was in agreement with earlier submissions made by

Holahanand Sears (1995), they submitted that the level of Self-Confidence was in fact a stronger predictor of performance than the level of skill or previous training. In a sixty-year study of more than one thousand high-IQ men and women tracked from early childhood to retirement, it was discovered that those who possessed Self-Confidence during their early years were most successful in their careers. This implied that library works should be carried out in self-confident and every librarian should possess this vital EI competency in order to be more effective in discharging his/her duties in the university library.

However, it can be noted that although librarians in the university library are expected to meet some of the information needs of the library users that seek for diverse information from the library collections, the fact remains that they are human beings that are limited in strength, knowledge and even skills. Having this basic knowledge of their limitations, they should not pose as having answers to all the library users' queries but they should refer those difficult queries to other sources (superior officers or resources) that can readily provide answers to their problems. In the same vein, library users should not be over-demanding in their quest for information from the library personnel and its resources; they should take cognizance of the librarians' limitations. Research question three showed that librarians were facing some challenges that affected their level of productivity in the university libraries. Specifically, it was showed that non-payment of similar allowances payable to other academic staff followed by inadequate employee recognition and marginalization of librarians by the university authority greatly affected job satisfaction of librarians in the university. It could be reiterated here that emotional intelligence of employees plays a crucial role in determining the general output of workers in any organization.

The study revealed unequal payment of allowances payable to other academic staff in the university as the highest problem affecting job satisfaction of librarians in most university libraries. This finding confirmed the submission of Nwosu et al (2013) that majority of librarians in Nigeria were being poorly paid and motivated. Unfortunately, some public university authorities maintained segregation administrative system; they were not treating their faculty members equally; there were some allowances paid to lecturers which were regarded by the university management as "core academic staff" but which were not paid to the librarians. It could be noted that with such composition, the morale of librarians in such university would be low and this would as well affected the level of their job satisfaction and productivity. It showed that librarians were not recognized as full academic staff of the university management and they were being treated as second class academic staff in the same university.

Hence, this apartheid management style must stop; if not there would be high rate of staff turnover in the public university library.

The result of inadequate recognition of librarians in most Nigerian university system has contradicted the submissions of Russell (2008) as well as [Massachusetts Institute of Technology](#) (2014) who noted in their findings that employee recognitions a motivational element that could be applied in the managerial level to motivate the employees for better job performance and being more innovative. They further stressed that recognition is a positive feedback that enables employees know that they are valued and appreciated by their employers and co-workers.

Thus, emotional intelligence enhances productivity of workers in any organization especially in the public university libraries as an emotionally stabled worker is a happy and productive worker. It is therefore expedient for every “manager to take initiative in finding out those factors that improve ‘emotional intelligent capabilities’ and job satisfaction of the subordinates” (Vijayabanu & Swaminathan, 2016, p. 1638) in order to boost productivity and enhances retention of the experienced workforce in the organization.

Furthermore, it can be revealed from the findings and analysis presented in Table 5, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that there was a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in the public university libraries in Nigeria ($r = 0.032$, $P < 0.05$). The finding corresponds with previous studies conducted by some scholars; few of these studies were here presented: Salovey and Mayer (1990), Goleman (2005), Sahdat et al (2011), Zaki et al (2012), Javidparvar et al (2013), Kalitani (2013), Orluwene and Wachukwu (2014) and Zobisch (2014) to establish the relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of employees in the organization. This showed that a worker who had a good knowledge of his/her emotion would be more productive than other workers who have no such knowledge.

7. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 Summary of Major Findings

1. Librarians’ level of productivity was high judging by the average mean score of 3.39 on the scale of 4. They considered their contribution to students’ academic success and the universities’ success in getting more courses accredited as major measures of their level of productivity.
2. Librarians’ level of emotional intelligence was also high judging by the average mean score of 3.32 on the scale of 4. They attributed this to their relational

management of the library users as well as their self-awareness ability as major measures of their emotional intelligence in the university system.

3. Challenging issues facing university librarians' productivity was very high judging by the average mean score of 3.02 on the scale of 4. They attributed these to on-payment of similar allowances payable to other academic staff as well as lack of adequate recognition and marginalization of librarians by the university authorities.

7.2 Conclusion

The study had succeeded in disabusing the earlier submission of low level productivity of library personnel judging from its findings. It was directed towards librarians' welfare and personal issues such as emotional intelligence and their level of productivity in the university libraries. The study established that emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in the Nigerian public university libraries were positively correlated.

Besides, the study confirmed the assertion that emotional intelligence enhances productivity of workers in any organization especially in the public university libraries as an emotionally stabled librarian is a productive librarian. Therefore, in the public university institutions, the welfare and personal issues of librarians should be taken seriously. They should be adequately and fairly motivated so as to enable them emotionally stabled and discharge their duties effectively. It is expedient for the university authorities to seek and put in place those motivating factors that would enhance the emotional intelligence and productivity of workers in the university community. Hence, the findings and recommendations that emanated from this study would be relevant to our local needs in Nigeria and beyond.

7.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings and challenges that were revealed in this study, the following recommendations are hereby proffered as the way forward:

1. The study revealed decrease in paper publications among librarians and other faculty members in the last two years. This was attributed to general observation that most Nigerian public university libraries were stocked with irrelevant, old and obsolete resources that could not be used for any meaningful research work. It is therefore imperative for the university libraries in Nigeria to be stocked with current and relevant educational resources that would boost high class research works.

2. Lower level of social awareness emotional intelligence component when compared with that of relationship management. This suggested that librarians were lacking organization awareness competency. Librarians were expected to have full knowledge of the entire organization they were expected to serve. They were to carry out users' analysis in order to have full knowledge of their information needs. This could be done through questionnaire, internal memo to heads of department and experts on each subject field soliciting for their input in the selection process, publishers' catalogues as well as relevant book vendor list could be sent to each subject experts to select appropriate texts, amongst other methods.
3. The study equally revealed that job satisfaction and productivity of librarians in most Nigerian public university libraries were been challenged by non-payment of similar allowances payable to other academic staff as well as inadequate employee recognition and marginalization of librarians by the university authorities. The university authorities should mete out equal treatment to every academic staff and none should be marginalized nor given higher priority over the others. In other words, no academic staff should be treated as a core staff or regarded as a very important personality (VIP) over the others. Hence, they should be paid equal salaries and allowances in line with the government approved salary structures. Also, librarians should be given adequate recognition as custodians and managers of information resources needed in supporting the curricula of each academic programme in the university system.

7.4 Implication of the Study

The findings of this study indicated that Librarians in Nigerian Universities saw their level of job satisfaction and productivity as very high. They attributed this to being recognised by the authorities as well as good leadership styles that were practised as the greatest measures of their job satisfaction in the university system. They considered their contribution to students' academic success and the universities' success in getting more courses accredited as major measures of their level of productivity. These would improve growth and development of the university system as there will be increase in student's enrolment and more new programmes will be accredited for the university.

Besides, the study equally revealed that motivation, emotional intelligence and human capital development jointly correlated with the job satisfaction and productivity of librarians in the Nigerian Public university libraries. This implies that a fairly motivated librarian who has good knowledge of his/her emotion and received relevant training coupled with constant career development, will have high level job satisfaction

and will be more productive in the university library. Also, the study affirmed that a satisfied worker is a productive worker.

On the whole, the study showed some challenging issues facing university librarians' job satisfaction and productivity was very high. They attributed these to on-payment of similar allowances payable to other academic staff as well as lack of adequate recognition and marginalization of librarians by the university authorities. If these problems were not checked, they will lead to low productivity and loss of experienced librarians in the university system. Also, the finding of this study in the area of inadequate funding of library resources; will result in inadequate provision of relevant educational resources to support the curricula and programmes in the university system.

7.5 Contribution to Knowledge

The centrality of the findings of this study established the link between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria. The findings of this study confirmed the dearth of research in investigating the relationships between welfare and personal issues such as emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in public universities in Nigeria and beyond. Thus, this study has created a platform through which the existed gap has been filled and a bedrock through which future research could be based.

7.6 Suggestions for Further Studies

The present study focused on the emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in public University libraries in Nigeria. The study surveyed all the public universities in North-Central, North-West, South-East and South-West geopolitical zones in Nigeria. Therefore, the following areas of study are suggested for further research:

1. An investigation on how librarians in the Public Universities in North-East and South-South geopolitical zones of Nigeria perceive the factors identified in this study in relationship to their job satisfaction and productivity.
2. A study on how librarians in the Private Universities in Nigeria perceive the factors identified in this study in relationship to their emotional intelligence and productivity.
3. A study on how librarians in other Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria perceive the factors identified in this study in relationship to their emotional intelligence and productivity.
4. A study on how the perceptions of librarians in the Public Universities in Nigeria compare with those of the librarians in Private Universities.

5. This study limits itself to only twenty six emotional intelligence competencies, it is important to further investigate into various other emotional intelligence competencies that would boost the productivity of workers in the university system or in similar institutions of higher learning

7.7 Limitation of the Study

One of the major constraints of this study was that it was difficult to retrieve the administered research instrument from many librarians as most of them refused to complete it with an excuse that the instrument is too voluminous, some even refused to participate in the study. This situation was solved by the researcher and those that worked with him as they had to convince and persistently pleaded with the respondents through constant telephone calls and regular emails sent to remind them. He personally pleaded with others that were in nearby universities for their assistance in completing the research instrument. Also, he sent money to some of his Research Assistants as their compensation and to buy soft drinks for the respondents. This motivating factor greatly improved the return rate of the research instrument. Nevertheless, many librarians especially in the Northern States of Nigeria showed great enthusiasm towards the study and they completed the instrument sent to them promptly. Besides, finance also constituted a great hindrance, but God divinely helped the researcher. He got credit facilities from banks, individuals and cooperative societies of his office to finance the programme. However, these limitations were not insurmountable, as the researcher worked around them to record success in the outcome of the research.

References

1. Abdullah-Sani, M.K.J.et al (2013). Assessing the Emotional Intelligence Profile of Public Librarians in Malaysia: Descriptive Analysis. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal). Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1047> on 27/03/14
2. Adeyokun, B.O. & Yaya, J.A. (2010). Consortium building of educational materials in Nigerian libraries. *Jewel Journal of Librarianship*, 2, 128 – 137.
3. Affandi, H. & Raza, N. (2013). Leaders' emotional intelligence and its outcomes, a study of medical professionals in Pakistan. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 5 (7), 279-297. Available online at <http://www.ijcrb.webs.com>.

4. Afolabi, A. & Omole, J.P. (2010). Influence of emotional intelligence and gender on job performance and job satisfaction among Nigerian policemen. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 2 (3), 147-154.
5. Aina, L. O. (2004). *Library and Information Science Text for Africa*. Ibadan: Third World Services Limited.
6. Ajala, E. M. (2012). The Influence of workplace environment on workers' welfare, performance and productivity. *The African Symposium: An online Journal of the African Educational Research Network*, 12 (1), 141-149. Available online at: <http://www.ncsu.edu/aern/TAS12.1/TAS12.1Ajala.pdf>
7. Akinboye, J.O. (2003). *Creativity, Innovation and Success*. Ibadan: Stirling-Horden Publishers Ltd.
8. Ali, A.Y.S., Ali, A.A. & Adan, A.A. (2013). Working conditions and employees' productivity in manufacturing companies in sub-Saharan African context: case of Somalia. *Educational Research International*, 2(2), 67 – 78. Available online at: www.savap.org.pk
9. Anonymous author (n.d). Term paper on impact of emotional intelligence on employee's performance. Retrieved from <http://www.BesplatniSeminarskiRadovi.com> on 18/10/14.
10. Azuka, B.F. & Kurumeh, M.S. (2015). Effects of emotional intelligence skills acquisition on students' achievement in senior secondary school geometry in Keffi education zone, Nasarrawa State, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Education and E-Learning* (ISSN: 2321-2454), 243 – 257. Available at: www.ajouronline.com.
11. Babalola, G.A. & Nwalo, K.I.N. (2013). Influence of job motivation on the productivity of librarians in colleges of education in Nigeria. *Information and Knowledge Management*, 3 (5), 70-75. Retrieved from: www.iiste.org on 27/02/14.
12. Bachman, J., et al (2000). Emotional intelligence in the collection of debt. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 8 (3), 176-182.
13. Bar-On, R. (2000). "Emotional and Social Intelligence: Insights from the Emotional Quotient Inventory", in R. Bar-On & J. D. A. Parker (Eds.) (2000) *The Handbook of Emotional Intelligence: Theory, Development, Assessment, and Application at Home, School, and in the Workplace*, (pp. 363-388). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
14. Bibi, A., Lanrong, Y., Haseeb, M. & Ahmad, I. (2012). The Effect of human resource management practices on employees' job satisfaction on the universities of Pakistan. *Business Management Dynamics*, 1 (12), 1-14.

15. Boston University School of Public Health (2013). The Social cognitive theory. Retrieved on 30/08/14 from <http://sphweb.bumc.bu.edu/otlt/MPH-Modules/SB/.../SB721-Models5.html>
16. Boyatzis, R., Goleman, D. & Rhee, K. (2000). Clustering competence in emotional intelligence: Insights from the emotional competence inventory (ECI). In R. Baron and J.D.A. Parker (Eds.), *Handbook of Emotional Intelligence*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
17. Browne, C., George-Curran, R. & Smith, M. (2003). The role of emotional intelligence in the career commitment and decision making process. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 11(4), 379-392.
18. Budd, J. M. (2007). *The Academic Library: Its Context, its Purpose, and its Operation*. Englewood, CO: Libraries Unlimited.
19. Chaudhary, N. & Sharma, B. (2012). Impact of employee motivation on performance (productivity) in private organization. *International Journal of Business Trends and Technology*, 2 (4), 29-35.
20. Cheng, T. (2016). Research methods part 4: The correlational design. Retrieved on 28th April, 2016 from <http://www.psych2go.net/research-methods-part-4-the-correlational-design/>
21. Chia, Y.M. (2005). Job offers of multi-national accounting firms: the effects of emotional intelligence, extracurricular activities, and academic performance. *Accounting Education*, 86 (7), 75 - 93.
22. Craig, P. (2008). The relationship between the emotional intelligence of the principal and teacher job satisfaction. Dissertations available from ProQuest.
23. Crant, J.M. (1995). The proactive personality scale and objective job performance among real estate agents. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 80.
24. Dost, M.K.B., Rehman, Z., & Tariq, S. (2012). The Organizations having high level of glass ceiling, has lower productivity due to lack of employee commitment. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 1 (8), 93-103.
25. Dubre, O. (2013). Employee motivation and organizational performance. *Review of Applied Socio-Economic Research*, 5 (1), 53-60. Available online at <http://www.reaser.eu>
26. EBSCO Competency Center (2013). Emotional intelligence and relationships. Retrieved on 18/10/14 from <http://www.ebscohost.com>
27. Ghoniem, A. ElKhouly, S., Mohsen, G. & Ibrahim, M. (2011). Impact of emotional intelligence and gender on job satisfaction among Egyptian Government sector employees. *Current Research Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(1), 22-27
28. Goleman, D. (2005). *Emotional Intelligence*. New York: Bentam Book.

29. -----(2002). "An EI-based theory of performance". In *the Emotionally Intelligent Workplace* edited by: Cary Cherniss and Daniel Goleman. Consortium for Research on Emotional Intelligence in Organizations. Available online at: www.eiconsortium.org
30. -----(1998). Daniel Goleman's five components of emotional intelligence. Available at <http://www.sonoma.edu/users/swijlink/teaching/philosophy.../goleman.htm>.
31. -----(1995a). *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More than IQ*. New York: Bantam Books.
32. -----(1995b). *Emotional intelligence*. New York: Bantam Books.
33. Gundecha, M.M. (2012). *Study of Factors Affecting Labour Productivity at a Building Construction Project in the USA: Web Survey*. Unpublished dissertation submitted to the Graduate Faculty of the North Dakota State University of Agriculture and Applied Science.
34. Hernon, P., Giesecke, J., & Alire, C. A. (2007): *Academic Librarians as Emotionally Intelligent Leaders*. Westport, CT: Greenwood Publishing Group.
35. Holahan, C.K. & Sears, R.R. (1995). *The Gifted Group in Later Maturity*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
36. Javidparvar, L., Hosseini, T.A. & Berjisian, R. (2013). The Relationship between emotional intelligence and leadership performance in primary schools managers of Isfahan. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 3(8), 1-10. Retrieved on 18/10/14 from <http://www.ijsrp.org>
37. Kahtani, A. A. (2013). Employee emotional intelligence and employee performance in the higher education institutions in Saudi Arabia: A Proposed theoretical framework. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 4 (9), 81-95.
38. Khokhar, C.P. & Kush, T. (2009). Emotional intelligence and work performance among executive. *Europe Journal of Psychology*, 1, 1-11.
39. Kowalczyk, D. (2015). Correlational research: Definition, purpose & examples. Retrieved on 28th April, 2016 from <http://www.study.com/.../correlational-research-definition-purpose-examples.html>
40. Krishnakumar, R. & Lalitha, S. (2014). A Study on emotional intelligence and occupational stress. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Research*, 2, 21-24. Available at <http://ijmcr.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/06/paper19633-636.pdf>
41. Maraichelvi, A. & Rajan, S. (2013). The relationship between emotional intelligence and the academic performance among final year under graduates.

- Universal Journal of Psychology*, 1 (2), 41-45. Retrieved from <http://www.hrpub.org>.DOI: 10.13189/ujp.2013.010203
42. Maraichelvi, A. & Rajan, S. (2013). The relationship between emotional intelligence and the academic performance among final year under graduates. *Universal Journal of Psychology*, 1 (2), 41-45. Retrieved from <http://www.hrpub.org>.DOI: 10.13189/ujp.2013.010203
43. Masrek, M. N. Abdullah-Sani, M. J. & Jamaludin, A. (2012). *Emotional Intelligence and Occupational Performance among Malaysian Librarians*. Malaysia: Research Management Institute (RMI) Universiti Teknologi Mara.
44. [Massachusetts Institute of Technology](http://www.mit.edu) (2014). Performance Development: Employee Recognition. Retrieved from <http://hrweb.mit.edu/performance-development/employee-recognition> on 18/09/14.
45. Mathis. R. L. & Jackson, J. H. (2003). *Human Resource Management*, (10th edition). Sg: Thomson South-Western.
46. Mayer, J. D. & Salovey, P. (1990). Perceiving affective content in ambiguous visual stimuli: A component of emotional intelligence. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 54, 772-781.
47. Messersmith, J. (2007). Managing work-life conflict among information technology workers. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 46, 429-451
48. Mill, J., & Lodge, D. (2006). Affect, emotional intelligence and librarian-user interaction. *Library Review*, 55(9), 587-597.
49. Murray, R. A. (1999). Job satisfaction of professional and para-professional library staff at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. Unpublished Master's paper for the M.S. in L.S. degree.
50. Nachimias, D. & Nachimias, C.F. (1987). *Research Methods in the Social Sciences*, (3rd edition). New York: St. Martin's.
51. National Universities Commission (2015). List Of Nigerian Universities and Years Founded. Retrieved on 24/06/15 from <http://www.nuc.edu.ng/pages/universities.asp>
52. Nikolaou, I. & Tsaousis, I. (2002). Emotional intelligence in the workplace: Exploring its Effects on Occupational Stress and Organisational Commitment. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 10 (4), 327 – 342.
53. Nwosu, C.O., Ugwoegbu, U. & Okeke, I. (2013). Levels of Motivation as Correlates of Librarians' Task Performance in University Libraries In South – East, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 8 (4), 81- 83.

54. Ogungbeni, J., Ogungbo, W. & Yaya, J.A. (2013). Emotional Intelligence, Job Satisfaction and Librarians' Performance. *Journal of Research in Education and Society*, 4(1), 53- 61.
55. Ogunsanwo, G.A. (2012, December). *You and Your Job: Attitude Required for Improving Performance and Productivity*. Paper presented at the Training Workshop for Junior Staff of Library Unit of Yaba College of Technology. Held at Center for Management Development (CMD), Magodo, Lagos, December.
56. Okonedo, S., Popoola, S.O., Emmanuel, S.O. & Bamigboye, O.B. (2015). Correlational Analysis of Demographic Factors, Self-Concept and Research Productivity of Librarians in Public Universities in South-West, Nigeria. *International Journal of Library Science*, 4 (3), 43-52. DOI: 10.5923/j.library.20150403.01
57. Olomolaiye, P. O., Wahab, K., & Price, A. (1998). Problems Influencing Craftsman Productivity in Nigeria. *Building Environment Journal*, 22 (4), 317-323.
58. Orluwene, G. W. & Wachikwu, T. (2014). Dimensions of Emotional Intelligence as Predictors of Job Involvement among Teachers. *International Journal of Development and Emerging Economics*, 2 (1), 8-18. Available online at: www.ea-journals.org.
59. Parham, D. (2014). Definition, importance and determinants of productivity. Retrieved on 05/04/16 from http://s3.amazonaws.com/zanran_storage/economics.adelaide.edu.au/ContentPages/2523797741.pdf
60. Petrides, K. V. Niven, L. & Mouskounti, T. (2006). The trait emotional intelligence of ballet dancers and musicians. *Psicothema*, 18: 101-107.
61. Rahgozar, H. et al (2012). A Study of the relation between emotional intelligence and decision making style (case study: school principals' of Shiraz City). *Journal of Basic Applied Scientific Research*, 2 (1 2), 12115-12120.
62. Rizi, R. M., Azadi, A., Farsani, M. E. & Aroufzad, S. (2013). Relationship between leadership styles and job satisfaction among physical education organizations employees. *European Journal of Sports and Exercise Science*, 2 (1), 7-11. Available online at www.scholarsresearchlibrary.com
63. Rosier, R.H. (1996). *The Competency Model Handbook*, volume 3. Boston: Linkage
64. Rozell, E. J., Pettijohn, C. E. & Parker, R. S. (2004). Customer-oriented selling: Exploring the roles of emotional intelligence and organizational commitment. *Psychology & Marketing*, 21(6), 405-424.
65. Russell, B. (2008). *The Analysis of Mind*. San Francisco: Biblio Bazaar, LLC

66. Sahdat, M., Sajjad, S.I., Farooq, M.U. & Rehman, K. (2011). Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Productivity: A Conceptual Study. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 15 (6), 821-825, ISSN 1818-4952.
67. Sinclair, R.R., Tucker, J.S., Cullen, J.C., & Wright, C. (2005). Performance differences among four organizational commitment profiles. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 90 (6), 1280-1287.
68. Singh, D. (2005). *Emotional Intelligence at Work: A Professional Guide*. New Delhi: Response Book.
69. Singh, J.K. & Jain, M. (2013). A Study of employee's job satisfaction and its impact on their performance. *Journal of Indian Research*, 1(4), 105- 111.
70. Sirca, N.T., Babnik, K. & Breznik, K. (2012). The relationship between human resource development system and job satisfaction. *Management Knowledge and Learning International Conference*, 977 – 987.
71. Stock, B. (2010). Emotional Intelligence Competencies. Retrieved on 05/10/14 from <http://Info@ByronStock.com>
72. Suleiman, W. (2013). A Study of causes of poor attitude to work among workers of both public and private sectors organizations in Bauchi State-Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3 (7), 143-152. Available online at <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v3-i7/16>. DOI: 10.6007/IJARBS/v3-i7/16.
73. Swanson, A. & Zobisch, P. (2014). Emotional Intelligence Understanding among Real Estate Professionals. *Global Journal of Business Research*, 8 (5), 9-16. Available Online at: www.Theibfr.Org
74. Vijayabanu, U. & Swaminathan, V.D. (2016). Relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment on coping with organization change. *International Journal of Information Research and Review*, 3 (1), 1636-1639.
75. Vyas, K. (2005). Emotional Intelligence Competencies. Retrieved from <http://www.kartikvyas.com> on 05/10/14
76. Wae, M. (2010). *Inter Relationship Between Personality, Emotional Intelligence, and Job Satisfaction of Bank Employees*. Unpublished PhD thesis, University Utara Malaysia.
77. Woods, C. (2014). Job Enrichment: Definition, Advantages, Disadvantages & Examples. Retrieved on 08/09/14 from <http://www.education-portal.com/.../job-enrichment-definition-advantages-disadvant>
78. Yahyazadeh-Jeloudar, S. & Lotfi-Goodarzi, F. (2012). Teachers' emotional intelligence and its relationship with job satisfaction. *Advances in Education*, 1 (1), 4-9

79. Yamoah, E.E. (2013). Relationship between compensation and employee productivity. *Singapore Journal of Business Economics and Management Studies*, 2 (1), 110-114.
80. Yaya, J.A. (2007). *Job Motivation and Emotional Intelligence as correlates of Librarians' Job Performance in selected University Libraries in South West, Nigeria*. Unpublished Dissertation, University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.
81. Yong, B. (2013). Relationship between Emotional Intelligence, Motivation, Integrity, Spirituality, Mentoring and Servant Leadership practices. *Arts and Sciences Journal*, 2013, 1 – 6, Article ID: ASSJ – 67. Available online at: <http://astonjournals.com/assj>.
82. Zaki, A.R.; Hasan, S.S. &Manzoor, M. (2012).Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Employees' Leadership Skills – Strategic Approach towards Organizational Stability. *Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 4(3), 32-40. Retrieved from <http://www.iosrjournals.org> on18/10/14.
83. Zeidner, M., Matthews, G. & Roberts, R.D. (2009).*What We Know About Emotional Intelligence: How it Affects Learning, Work, Relationships, and Our Mental Health*. Cambridge: Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT).
84. Ziv, T. (2014). What is Emotional Competence? Retrieved on 05/10/14 from <http://www.drtaiaziv.com/9.html>

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